

Cyber-Physical Intensive Care Medical System for **Covid-19**

Grant Agreement 101016000

D4.1 SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES (SSH) FRAMEWORK FOR CO-CREATING ICU HUBS

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In this deliverable, we outline the SSH-framework that needs to inform the successful, sustainable and responsible implementation of CPS4TIC in the course of ICU4Covid and beyond. We develop an understanding of the ICU as an arrangement of humans, machines and practices that will inevitably be transformed by the introduction of new technological systems. This calls for putting in place co-creation environments in each of the ICU Hubs that allow the implementation process to be sensitive to local circumstances and the perspectives of different users.

SSH FRAMEWORK FOR CO-CREATING ICU HUBS

Environment

Establish environments for successful co-creation

ENVIRONMENT FOR CO-CREATION

To assure sustainability and long-term success of the implemented Cyber-Physical System for Telemedicine and Intensive Care (CPS4TIC), the project will put in place co-creation environments in each ICU Hub. Co-creation is a process that includes the stakeholders affected by the implementation to assure solutions are attuned to the different expectations, knowledges and needs. Through the SSH framework, we identify the stakeholders, engage with their specific approaches towards implementation, translate their needs, values and concerns in social user requirements that then can be considered in the adaptive process of CPS4TIC implementation.

Document

Document changes in socio-technical arrangement of ICU

CHANGES IN THE SOCIO-TECHNICAL ARRANGEMENT OF THE ICU

Experiences and observations of implementing telemedical, robotics and data driven support systems from SSH research show that these technologies (CPS4TIC) can have profound and (un)expected impacts on social and technical arrangements and practices within healthcare settings — the ICUs. Documenting the implementation process and, in particular, the experiences, observations and concerns of diverse users helps to identify and understand potential socio-technical challenges. It will help to prevent them or identify adequate solutions early in the process.

Specific

Consider local specificities and user ecologies

LOCAL SPECIFICITIES & USER ECOLOGIES

Research in SSH has highlighted the relevance of the local contexts where (healthcare) technologies are to be implemented and the specific ecologies of users that collectively care for ICU patients at these sites. Knowing local conditions and arrangements of healthcare in the participating hospitals — diverging regulatory frameworks regarding healthcare, different resources for implementing CPS4TIC and established routines of providing healthcare — and the challenges they pose is key for the scalability of CPS4TIC to new ICU Hubs.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Explanation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIDSS	AI-driven Decision Support Systems
CPS4TIC	Cyber-Physical System for Telemedicine and Intensive Care
DAE	Digital Agenda for Europe
DG SANTE	Directorate General for Health and Food Safety
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DSA	Digital Services Act
EBCC	Experience-Based Co-Creation
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ICU	Intensive Care Unit
MFF	Multiannual Financial Framework
PPI	Public Procurement of Innovative Solutions
PPP	Public Private Partnership in Robotics
RI	Responsible Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities

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1 INTRODUCTION – WHAT IS AT STAKE?

The current situation, a global pandemic caused by a new virus, has created not only more public, political and governance awareness for the importance of well-functioning Intensive Care Units (ICUs), but also for the challenges medical professionals working in the ICUs have to face. Indeed, the situation became rapidly and drastically critical, where such conditions could not be ensured. Especially the difficult care and treatment situation that is necessary when engaging with patients that carry an infectious virus like COVID-19 makes adjustments to the everyday practices of all stakeholders involved necessary. This comprises (but is not limited to) medical professionals, patients and their relatives. Moreover, the pandemic also made visible that Intensive Care specialists are unevenly distributed among centres and periphery in hospital networks.

System developers and providers together with clinical and life scientists have succeeded in rapidly developing and adapting a cyber-physical system for the specific purpose of addressing the challenges for Intensive Care caused by COVID-19. The developed Cyber-Physical System for Telemedicine and Intensive Care (CPS4TIC) ensures efficient and effective diagnosis and treatment of COVID-19 patients, while reducing the risk of infection. It is used at sites, which successfully managed the first wave of COVID-19 for several hundreds of patients and many hundreds of teleconsultations. The ICU4Covid project aims at advancing the developed CPS4TIC to large scale deployment with full involvement of the end-users, hospitals and health authorities.

The basic principle (as shown in Figure 1) is that CPS4TIC enables existing or new ICU structures to transform into and operate as one ICU Hub with one central ICU and connected ICUs in 'peripheral' hospitals. Large scale pilots and deployment will be performed in real ICU settings located in four different countries (Austria, Germany, Greece and Portugal) involving more than 15.000 patients per year at large university hospitals as well as connected peripheral hospitals with a coverage range of approximately 45 million citizens. This means that next to delivering a technological solution for this healthcare challenge, it will also be essential to carefully consider that it needs to be implemented not only in rather different socio-cultural contexts, but also find a fit with the specificities of local institutional contexts and healthcare systems.

The CPS4TIC consists of a telemedicine cockpit in the central ICU, telemedicine consoles at each peripheral hospital, a connector platform and smart bedside hubs. The latter will also include robotic arms at the bedsides of both, the central telemonitoring hospitals as well as the peripheral telemonitored hospitals. The ICU Hub operates telemedicine, continuous real-time telemonitoring and bedside smart care environment (e.g. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced decision support systems). The bedside smart care environment also reduces significantly the risk of infection for the healthcare workforce in both, the central and

Figure 1 - 4 ICU Hubs

the peripheral hospitals. Several ICU Hubs can further cooperate in a cluster to provide additional local/regional support, share knowledge or updates of CPS (Cyber Physical Systems) decision-support models.

Broadening the availability of this technological infrastructure is meant to contribute in times of the crisis to improving access to healthcare, to providing sufficient capacity for treating patients irrespective of e.g. age, to increasing the quality of healthcare and to reducing the risk of infection through newest developments (such as CPS supported decision making). Multiplying the availability of intensive care specialists also in more peripheral hospitals is an essential step in this direction. But also beyond the current crisis, these telemedical systems can benefit the work in ICUs by creating a safer environment for medical professionals and patients.

Having briefly sketched the technological innovation at the core of ICU4Covid, it is obvious that in order to make the transformation successful, the project needs to be sensitive towards the societal dimension relevant to ICU4Covid, i.e. to the systemic and institutional aspects of the healthcare system and how it is understood, supported, and shaped by the respective societal environments. Simultaneously we also have to be attentive to the social dimensions, as this technological transformation of the ICU will affect the work and care environments for medical professionals, patients and their social environment as well as for caregivers in profound ways.

Without any doubt, one of the biggest challenges when aiming to develop the ICU of the future is to assure that digital innovations available are *actually adopted* by all those involved in the ICU, i.e. by medical doctors, nursing staff, patients and their families as well as hospital administrations and integrated into daily practices at different sites. Implementation research in the medical field has frequently pointed to the fact, that interventions often fail to be fully "implemented into routine practice and policy" and that this goes hand in hand with "an effortful, unpredictable and typically slow process" (Hull et al., 2019, p. 2) of integrating innovation into pre-existing structures and practices. There has, indeed, been a long-standing concern that available digital technologies that could improve treatment or prevention are integrated into the everyday practices in medical environments only with hesitation and thus do not deliver, are not understood and embraced by patients/citizens and, thus, do not manage to improve patient care. As a consequence, neither patients nor medical professionals or the healthcare system more broadly speaking can benefit from potential outcomes if implementation does not work successfully. This explains why, in recent years, we can observe "increased and focused efforts to close the evidence-to-practice gap" (Hull et al., 2019, p. 2). Thus, more attention is given to the process of translating the evidence for a technological improvement, e.g. through the implementation of new digital means as in the case of the ICU4Covid project, into everyday practice in the ICU. However, simultaneously we have to be aware that while a successful implementation of the proposed technological solutions can contribute in important ways to solving some of the challenges at stake, more systematic or structural issues differing across sites might still persist.

Therefore, ICU4Covid will engage in a development and implementation process which is guided by the idea of "co-creation" and uses insights from implementation research. While

classic co-creation includes stakeholders already in the process of developing technological solutions, in the case of ICU4Covid it aims at tailoring and adapting the process of implementation to local needs. Co-creation will hence assure that the implementation process of the CPS4TIC does not solely focus on the technical aspects of improvement, but also carefully considers the social and societal dimensions of such a transformative process. This approach should assure that implementation will take place in a collaborative manner together with different experts *and* stakeholders alike. This means that all those who develop the respective technical solutions are engaging with users and stakeholders along the process of development and implementation making use of experience, knowledge and the momentum to tackle the pandemic crisis. Participatory approaches enable a collectivization of the definition and elaboration of needs and solutions, and with this a form of mutual learning: the developers of technologies learn about users' ways of thinking, about work practices and everyday life in the ICU and they allow for diversity in users' voices, concerns, positions and contexts of use. Users, on the other hand, also engage in learning along the whole process of implementation aligning their own experiences and forms of knowledge with what the new technological possibilities can offer.

The task of Workpackage 4 in the ICU4Covid project is to develop and put in place a lively co-creation environment to assure a smooth *socio*-technical development of the ICU Hubs and its socially compatible scalability, being attentive to the diverse needs and concerns of future direct and indirect users. This should allow to better understand and adapt the new arrangements of practices and processes that emerge out of the implementation of these tech innovations in the ICU Hubs and how this improves the overall situation of care for patients. Thus, a comparative approach between the different ICU Hubs, as well as a careful consideration of "centers" and "peripheries" will sensitize to the dimensions that need attention when implementing the CPS4TIC in the ICU Hubs.

The aim of this deliverable 4.1 "SSH Framework for Co-creating ICU Hubs" is to develop and outline the social sciences and humanities (SSH) framework for accompanying the project's implementation and rollout process. This means to spell out the understanding of what is at stake from a social and societal perspective when implementing new digital capacities in the context of an ICU and reflect what needs to be considered in doing so across different sites. This report thus outlines the concepts that underpin the processes of co-creation that will be implemented in the project and positions the ICU4Covid approach in the debates around these technologies on the EU level as well as in the social science literature. The aim is, thus, to spell out what such a socio-technical project needs to consider in the different stages of its implementation process in order to become sustainable, empowering, caring and adaptable to ever new developments and challenges. In addition, it highlights some of the areas where preconceived assumptions might cause problems in the short- or long-term.

This report will therefore be structured in three chapters and a conclusion/summary of key insights. It will start in **chapter 2** which focuses on the co-creation process, spell out our basic understanding of co-creation, identify what aspects will need close consideration, but also outline the conceptual frames that are used. **Chapter 3** summarizes key lines of discussions and developments on the EU level concerning the technologies applied through the ICU4Covid

project. This is important in order to embed developments in ICU4Covid into a wider evolution taking place in these domains and consider issues raised in these contexts. **Chapter 4** will then identify and summarize the key insights from social science analyses around the technological applications that are central to the project: 1) telemedical care, 2) data science, 3) AI-driven decision-support systems and 4) robotics. The conclusions presented in **chapter 5** will identify identified tasks crucial for realising a context-sensitive atmosphere of co-creation in the different ICU Hubs of the ICU4Covid project. They will form a basis for deliverable 4.2 “Design the Co-Creation Process” which will specifically describe the set-up of the co-creation environment(s) and the methodological approaches that will be used.

2 CO-CREATING ICU HUBS – KEY CONCEPTS

In this chapter we will outline our basic understanding of how the social and the technological come together in re-organising the ICU on the basis of the proposed CPS4TIC. To do so, we will structure the chapter in two main parts. In the first part (**chapter 2.1**), we will reflect on the values and practices that should guide the mission-oriented innovation process that the ICU4Covid project will engage in. To this end, we will draw on conceptual discussions, as well as on some of the more practical experiences with the *Responsible Research and Innovation* (RRI) approach, as defined in the framework of Horizon 2020 by the European Commission, and point to the kinds of reflections and engagements this calls for. The second, and much larger part (**chapter 2.2**), will then outline our understanding of co-creation as practiced in this project and argue why it is essential when wanting to successfully accompany and drive the implementation of the CPS4TIC across different sites and healthcare environments (**chapter 2.2.1**). The aim is to develop a framework that supports

- (1) analytic depth when studying the social/societal phenomena,
- (2) consistent characterization of features of the project environment and relationships between key elements,
- (3) well aligned data collection, analysis and interpretation,
- (4) a situated, yet consistent, organisation of implementation processes across different sites,
- (5) actor- and situation-specific empirical engagements within each co-creation environment for the different ICU Hubs and
- (6) a detailed description of the change processes and what can be learned for unfolding the deployment of the model beyond the case.

This will also include an explanation of how we conceptualise a single ICU Hub as well as the networked relations within them and between each other (**chapter 2.2.2**). Subsequently, we will reflect on what we call user and knowledge ecologies, so to explore the diversity of users working in the ICU Hubs we have to engage with as well as the different kinds of knowledges and experiences they potentially bring to the co-creation process (**chapter 2.2.3**). Finally, we engage with different versions of co-creation and how they can be used in the context of ICU4Covid (**chapter 2.2.4**).

2.1 Responsible (Research and) Innovation

What does the very notion of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) mean when we think about the process of implementing CPS4TIC in the ICU context? In the framework of ICU4Covid our focus will be on the responsible innovation aspect (RI), which stands for a collective commitment to carefully consider social and ethical aspects when innovating – in our case a system of medical care in the ICU and beyond (i.e. Koops et al., 2015). The basic conceptual idea behind this frame was to support “transparent, interactive process[es of innovation] by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view to

the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process” (von Schomberg, 2011, p. 9). In the case of ICU4Covid this would mean to perform the implementation process of CPS4TIC in ways that gives voice to a broad range of users and stakeholders such as medical professionals or patients.

Involving users and stakeholders into the processes of implementing innovation, can then – following this argumentation – be described as key

- to obtain relevant knowledge and experiences related to potential impacts of the introduction of innovations into the ICU and
- for effectively assessing both outcomes and options in terms of needs of different stakeholders and moral values at stake.

To care for such insights should then become “functional requirements for design and development of new research, products, and services” (van den Hoven et al., 2013).

RI can thus be understood as a response to a growing awareness that innovations might come with unintended consequences and thus not necessarily live up to the promises and visions developed at the start of a transformation process. Simultaneously, by including a diverse set of users and stakeholders into the processes of integrating CPS4TIC into the ICU, we can expect innovations which integrate broader sets of values, needs and expectations. This is all the more important as in ICU4Covid we are addressing an innovation which is not solely a technical innovation, but transforms medical care and social worlds. RI can thus be seen as the attempt to ensure that both the process and outcome of innovation are acceptable and socially desirable and offer thus robust and potentially more sustainable solutions.

This means asking the normative question of “what counts as an ‘improvement’” and for whom (von Schomberg, 2013, p. 54). Here, processes of engagement and collective assessment – processes that integrate different groups of users and stakeholders – should allow a much more inclusive reflection of the value of innovations (Felt, 2018). This points to a shift in attention from the (market) value *of* innovation, or a simple assessment of potential harm, to the values that are embedded *in* and realized *through* innovations (Felt, 2017). Attending to the values related to innovation also acknowledges that different cultural contexts (in our case different traditions in understanding organizing healthcare in hospitals) potentially relate differently to the technologies to be implemented in ICU4Covid and show preferences for specific technical arrangements and not others. Therefore, the exact direction in which innovations re-assemble the ICU have to be carefully considered (Felt et al., 2007).

To turn RRI (we will use RI, as our focus is not research, but the innovation element) into a living concept, Stilgoe and co-authors (2013, p.1570) have identified four key dimensions which need specific attention and fostering throughout the processes of innovation: “anticipation, reflexivity, inclusion and responsiveness”¹. However, as Demers-Payette and co-authors (2016, p. 189) have argued, we will need to adapt “this approach as it relates to health care systems,

¹ For an overview of the questions to be asked under RRI see also (Owen & Pansera, 2019).

where the notion of responsibility is formalized within the legislative apparatus that govern health care and embedded, to varying extent, in health care providers' practices".

Thinking along these four RRI dimensions will allow us to better engage with the different aspects of re-assembling the ICU (Figure 2) and to identify when engaging with the different actors points of divergence and convergence, but also fill these dimensions with context specific meanings and potentially also add new dimensions.

Figure 2 - RI dimensions applied to the implementation process in ICU4Covid

- Anticipation** refers to systematically thinking about the many different potential outcomes when CPS4TIC gets implemented. It also means admitting our limited capacities for foresight and thus be attentive to gradual changes. Anticipatory thinking has a long-standing tradition in developing and implementing innovation. However, an RI approach calls for a much broader take: We have to consider how and for whom the integration of new technological means will change both the work and care environment(s) in the ICU4Covid project (e.g. Oudshoorn, 2011; Pols, 2012). It is important to be attentive of how different users and stakeholders envision the future of the ICU and thus move beyond an all too narrowly driven expert vision. This will also mean to integrate user needs which often run the danger of being overlooked in favour of a specific technological solution (Demers-Payette et al., 2016). This means also considering the balance between push and pull factors in anticipatory work.
- Reflexivity** invites us to critically question "one's own activities, commitments and assumptions, being aware of the limits of knowledge and being mindful that a particular framing of an issue may not be universally held" (Stilgoe et al., 2013, p. 1571). This means thinking about whose problems are solved by the specific innovative solution in the ICU,

whose work routines need to be adapted and what kinds of potentially different interests and commitments users and stakeholders can have. It also pushes us to consider absences, i.e. those elements that are getting less attention or are tacitly embedded in the innovation/implementation process, but, nevertheless, shape the process. This means collectively with the different actors working in the ICU reflecting also on their vision of the “value systems and principles that underpin the health care system and medical innovations” (Demers-Payette et al., 2016, p. 195).

- **Inclusion** draws our attention to questions of the distribution of power and who is given, or not given, voice in the evolution of any research and innovation process. In the ICU4Covid this means considering the uneven distribution of certain possibilities in the respective healthcare environment and reflecting, for example, what the very notion of rollout means (i.e. how adaptable are the solutions developed to different sites). It calls for different forms of user and stakeholder engagement in defining problems, identifying assumptions in framing problems, and in suggesting/developing, as well as assessing, solutions. This also reminds us that we need to look for those who, for whatever reason, might be excluded from any moments of implementation, but would be key to implement a sustainable system.
- **Responsiveness** highlights the need to conduct research and innovation in ways that allow rethinking and adjusting “courses of action while recognising the insufficiency of knowledge and control” (Stilgoe et al., 2013, p. 1572). For the ICU4Covid project, this means that the integration process needs to remain open to learning, gradual adaptation and change depending on the concrete situation. This also includes the question of scalability of solutions and how they need to be adapted in order to allow such a process. Societal and social needs and values expressed in practice and experiences made, can then be integrated into the implementation process. However, the challenge will lie in the fact that the project will need to “modulate medical innovation trajectories in a highly regulated environment” such as the hospital and thus make “the inevitable adjustments to innovation trajectories as they progress and”, in doing so mobilize the expectations and experiences of everyone involved (Demers-Payette et al., 2016).

Together, being attentive to these four dimensions of RI will allow us to accompany the implementation process in a way which makes the innovated form of the ICU more context-sensitive, robust and sustainable in the mid- and long-term.

2.2 Why co-creation matters for successful implementation

To support and bundle the efforts for creating new technologies that can help dealing with and ultimately containing COVID-19 and put in place better and more equally distributed treatment opportunities across Europe, the European Commission opened a special call for innovation actions for close-to-market support solutions as well as maturing innovative

solutions in May 2020². While there is a long-standing tradition in funding advances in the medical sector, one of the main challenges for this specific call is that the outcomes of the funded projects must be available within a relatively short amount of time, otherwise they cannot effectively offer support in the current situation. This is connected to the challenge of making developed technologies and the associated changes in the way healthcare is practiced transferable and fit to work in settings as diverse as we find them in the European healthcare landscape. The communication between the projects funded by the European Commission through this special call is thus crucial, not only for the exchange of knowledge, but especially for the generation of synergy effects between them³.

In this context, next to fostering technological innovation, we have witnessed a growing presence of methods of co-creation. It should support an enlargement of innovative capacities by integrating diverse sets of experiences and knowledge from future users into the very process of developing and implementing innovations and thus engage in agile and use case-focused innovation. The expectation is that such an integrative approach might allow to speed up innovation, through better integration of new technologies with pre-existing systems and applications and thus deliver better returns (van Dijk-de Vries et al., 2020; Bammer, 2019; Greenhalgh et al., 2016; Grol et al., 2013).

Andersen (2019), speaking to digital health developments more generally, pointed us to an interesting paradox. While the expectations that digital health will bring essential improvements to our healthcare systems are high and first promising prototypes connecting patients and healthcare providers are ready, the actual realisation to not reach their full potential. Andersen identifies the use context after implementation: “Too little time and effort is spent on configuring the systems and adapting the clinical practices and the day-to-day activities” (Anderson, 2019, p. 74) of those using the systems. While ICU4Covid focuses on a much more specific context than the one analysed by Andersen, there are take-aways which are important to consider. ICU4Covid should involve the different users all along the implementation of the system, engaging with their needs, concerns and value considerations. Especially the local specificities must be regarded. This will then allow to learn important lessons that often receive too little attention, lessons that can only be learned during ‘use time’, i.e. when digital technologies become an integral part of actual healthcare practices.

ICU4Covid will thus engage in a development and implementation process which is guided by the idea of co-creation and uses insights from implementation research (i.e. Grol et al., 2013). The aim is to put in place in each ICU Hub a co-creation environment, which will support the implementation process of these digital innovations. This means that ICU4Covid wants to assure that the implementation process takes place in a collaborative manner together with the different users, experts and stakeholders, engaging with them along the whole process (Greenhalgh et al., 2016). Bringing those developing and implementing technological

² Call by the European Commission, Topic ID SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2B:

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/sc1-phe-coronavirus-2020-2b>

³ We are planning to communicate with different projects of the call within the next months. Especially those projects that are engaging as well with the work environment of the ICU or with new technologies to monitor and treat COVID-19 patients are in our focus. For more information on these other projects see **chapter 3**.

innovations and those “living with its consequences” together in a co-creation process, should result in the sharing of responsibility for what is being developed throughout the whole process.

2.2.1 The process of co-creation – outlining the approach

In past years, the use of the notion of co-creation has been proliferating. However the ways in which it is defined and put in practice has varied considerably, depending on the challenge that is at the centre of the co-creation effort, on the people that should be involved and on the setting in which it should take place.

Co-creation in the way understood in ICU4Covid is shorthand for **a collaborative and process-oriented approach to innovation**, actively involving experts, stakeholders and users broadly speaking and being grounded in the idea that sharing ideas, knowledge and experiences during the implementation process leads to context-sensitive sustainable solutions that are caring, adaptable and empowering (see Figure 3).

Well beyond this definition, there are also clear indications that **co-creation processes also lead to more collective forms of ownership**, i.e. to the feeling of shared responsibility, when it comes to innovative healthcare environments and therefore **can assure more successful implementation processes**.

Figure 3 - Co-creation process in supporting implementation

The process of co-creation used in the context of implementing a CPS4TIC can be schematized as follows. At the core is the CO-CREATION process. The “CO” stands for collaborative, value and context sensitive as well as attentive to the social dimension of any innovation. “CREATION”, in turn, stands for an evolving (very often the notion of “agile” is used here,

meaning that previous knowledge is applied while continuing to learn from current experience to deliver innovations more smoothly and faster), innovative and open, which points to the inclusiveness and the diversity sensitivity of the process.

"Context sensitive" points to the fact that developing, adapting and implementing a CPS4TIC has to be attentive to

- different well-established healthcare systems,
- healthcare practices that are in place and have been established over time,
- varying regulatory frames (including ethical considerations),
- different pre-existing technological environments and related routines in the healthcare context, as well as
- cultural diversity and the related sets of values and practices, more widely speaking.

That is why it is not only essential to achieve technical interoperability, in the sense of aligning data gathering and analysis processes across sites, but it is also key to achieve "sociocultural interoperability" (Felt, Öchsner & Rae, 2020), i.e. to function well across the different sites of the ICU Hubs. All this, in turn, has to be seen in the context of a major healthcare crisis due to COVID-19.

The **outcome** of this co-creation process is the successful implementation of a CPS4TIC that is **caring, adaptable, sustainable and empowering (CASE)**.

CARING means that patients' and healthcare professionals' as well as wider societal needs and concerns have been considered sufficiently in the implementation process;

ADAPTABLE points to the need to develop and implement solutions that are able to be responsive to disruptions, hurdles as well as cultural differences expressed in practices of healthcare provision and consumption;

SUSTAINABLE draws our attention to the fact that a successful implementation needs to be able to assure sustainability on four different levels, these being social, financial, technological and infrastructural; and finally,

EMPOWERING underlines that such a technological innovation offers decision support but need to give its users' enough space to foster their capacity to make their own decisions and argue for specific choices.

Table 1 - Features of the ICU Hub to be aimed at

Co-creation is organised as **a process** integrated into the designing and implementing of the CPS4TIC and will be structured in three steps – explore, respond and document.

EXPLORE – this means *listening to and engaging with* different actor groups around the ICU, identifying needs and concerns (through different methods to be specified in D4.2) and spelling them out in form of “socio-technical user requirements” (and not only technical user requirements) which will be reported as part of D4.3 “User Requirements in ICU Hubs.”

RESPOND – *developing innovative solutions collectively*; make possible adaptations and rearrangements that meet the needs and concerns; do it in an iterative manner, which means integrating feedback much faster to gradually work towards a stable solution; furthermore, this phase will be devoted to *assess and validate the changes implemented*, which will be reported in D4.4 “Validation and Assessment Report”.

DOCUMENT – *carefully documenting contexts and processes as well as hurdles and outcomes* from the phases EXPLORE and RESPOND in order to learn from the implementation processes across the different sites; these finding will be condensed and reported in Deliverable 4.5 “Handbook for Co-Creating an ICU Hub” as a more general guide to consider social/societal elements when implementing technological/digital solutions into health care contexts.

Table 2 - Three phases in the circular co-creation process

To summarize: Given the potential of digital interventions to improve healthcare provision, it is crucial to pay specific attention to understand how users – patients (and their relatives), their medical doctors and nursing staff – integrate these digital innovations into the context of healthcare. Despite agreement on the importance of implementation research, quite frequently there is “insufficient detail on the context and implementation process that can hamper replication and scale-up of interventions” (Ross et al., 2018, p. 795; see also Pinnock et al., 2017; Proctor et al., 2013). On top of this, digital health interventions are “one example of complex interventions that have proved difficult to implement due to factors such as interoperability, cost, fit with existing systems, disruption to interactions between health professionals and patients, and poor implementation planning” as highlighted by Ross and co-authors (2018, p. 795).

Furthermore, it will be essential to reflect the social and ethics questions the introduction, for example, of an AI supported decision-making system brings with it. While there is a tremendous potential in using these digital innovations, we have to observe in practice how the introduction of AI creates changes in the relation between medical professionals, patients (and their families) and the AI-driven Decision Support System (AIDSS). This will open up questions of the conditions of trustworthiness (i.e. a need for a well-balanced expectation management (EGE, 2018)), of transparency (i.e. are the algorithms comprehensible and are the paths how an algorithm arrives at an output clear enough even when highly complex (Floridi et al., 2018)), of how the digital infrastructure of the ICU units will shift how agency is shared in decision-making, and finally of how all this impacts how responsibility is viewed as newly distributed (e.g. the role of human decision in relation to AI supported decision making, see **chapter 4.2**).

Participatory approaches enable a collectivization of the definition and elaboration of problems and solutions, and with this a form of mutual learning: technology developers learn about

user's ways of thinking, about work practices and everyday life in the ICU and they allow for diversity in users' voices, concerns, positions and contexts of use. It will be essential to better understand how medical professionals trust, rely on or comply to AI aided decision-making situations and where they see themselves with regard to their role in and the responsibility for final decision making. We know from the field of technology studies, that every innovation also brings new responsibility relations with it – we like to use Akrich's (1992) notion of new "geographies of responsibility" to point to the distributed character –, and therefore it is important to carefully see how the integration of digital technologies into the ICU will also change the relations, actions and interactions between the different actors involved.

In practical terms, in order to assure the processual approach, we will put in place and run so-called **co-creation environments** in each of the sites (concrete elaboration on the methods to be used for the specific situations will be delivered in D4.2 "Design of the Co-creation Process"). At different instances of the project, we will use specific methods to engage with diverse actors in the field, and will address a spectrum of problem areas from the technical to the social. At different points in time subset of the consortium partners will be involved and distinctive temporal and spatial aspects will come to matter. We will go to different places thus moving into a variety of institutional environments, encountering diverse cultural settings and engaging with specific sets of actors.

Within these co-creation environments, mutual engagement and learning will happen along the whole process of implementation. It will happen between those who implement the technologies, medical professionals, patients (and their families) and institutional actors in the respective hospitals – social scientists taking the role of translators between these different groups and their positions. At different moments of the implementation process and using different situation-adapted methods, we will collectively identify the issues and concerns of different user groups, formalize them as **socio-technical user requirements specifying preferred elements and functionalities** of the CPS4TIC, prioritize potential adaptations and **test and validate** them once implemented (see also Felt, Öchsner & Rae, 2019a).

Before going closer into the co-creation process, we want to clarify in a next step our understanding of the ICU and what is at stake when introducing a full-fledged CPS4TIC.

2.2.2 Conceptualising the ICU – Re-assembling the social and the technical

To best capture the social and societal dimensions relevant to this project, we need to outline a conceptual understanding of the ICU beyond its technological specifications. Making this basic understanding transparent, will offer an efficient way for using findings across diverse sites involved in the project. This is also essential, as it will allow us to deliver better explanations of implementation-related phenomena (successes or hurdles) and thus facilitate shared understandings of challenges and potential context specific solutions.

In this project we **conceptualise the ICU as a** complex social and technical assemblage – in short **socio-technical assemblage** (Latour, 2005) – that has to bring together, connect and align diverse actors, technologies, and institutions as well as regulations, practices, visions and values in order to be successful. This conceptualisation is key as it allows us to capture the implementation process both in its technological and social dimensions. In addition, it makes

us attentive to how values and visions matter and to how the many different elements come or do not come together smoothly.

Even though medical procedures and practices have always been entangled with technological solutions, new technologies still mean a disruption of established connections and force a change in the existing assemblages. From the use of seemingly banal objects such as plastic gloves for hygiene and safety, over dialysis machines to monitoring devices for patient statuses, all these technologies have transformed the way healthcare is practiced. At the same time their implementation in the everyday work practices of medical professionals and the everyday life of patients had to be learned first and was accompanied by changes in the matching healthcare legislation but also in the self-understandings of medical professionals as well as patients. At the same time, these implementation processes, the demands formulated by users and the specific ways these technologies were embedded in practices also contributed to shaping the technological innovations.

Concretely, such an approach is supportive to our co-creation approach deployed in this project as it draws our attention to

- the fact that in an ICU a large variety of elements, be they technical or social, have to be brought together and integrated in a stable manner in order to successfully function as a whole;
- the links between the different elements in the assemblage; this makes us look into the stability of the connections between the different elements are; we thus need to be attentive to both strong and weak ties in the network;
- the need to identify and revisit the diverse everyday practices in the ICU that emerge out of and stabilize a specific assemblage.

However, above all it makes us aware that with the introduction of technological innovations the whole network has to be re-arranged – that is why we speak of **re-assembling the ICU**. Indeed, in the case of the ICU4Covid project, hospitals are not starting from scratch, but the ICUs are already functioning entities with existing social and technological systems in place, so, to stick with our language they have already been assembled successfully. However, through introducing innovations and with the aim of improving the ICU to better respond to COVID-19 conditions, the whole assemblage undergoes more or less important re-arrangements. In this case we also have to consider the specific institutional context, the healthcare system in place, but also the wider socio-cultural environment in the different ICU Hubs that are distributed across Europe.

Figure 4 - The ICU as a socio-technical assemblage

The elements forming the ICU assemblage include

- human actors such as patients, medical professionals, pharmacists, IT staff ,;
- diverse kinds of technologies (visibly and invisibly) related to the ICU;
- institutional/organizational actors such as hospital providers, universities or ethics committees;
- established practices and relationships in care and medical intervention;
- regulations, norms and values (including ethics); technological, social, legal and ethical standards; data related issues such as security and privacy.

It is key to observe how all these diverse elements connect to each other, how they are assembled, to create a smoothly working whole – the ICU. Therefore, it is essential to be attentive to the different elements present in the assemblage and to **the multiple relationships between them**. This means carefully considering the ways in which different elements are connected and aligned so that they can form a coherent whole – the ICU as socio-technical assemblage.

Relationships can be of different strength; some need more work to hold than others. To describe what is happening during the creation and stabilisation of such an assemblage, two notions are important. We speak of “enrolment” when an effort is made to turn specific groups of actors into partners/supporters by considering and integrating their interests, values and concerns. To successfully enrol others, we need to achieve adequate “translations”, i.e. to bring interests of different actor/user groups in line to define and achieve the overall aim of the implementation process. At the same time, the assemblage can become fragile and break if an important actor leaves the assemblage, puts it in question or cuts off the relationship. Looking at the ICU as a socio-technical assemblage thus sensitizes us to the context-specific

rearrangements that happen but also to the dynamic processes when CPS4TIC is implemented in the ICU Hubs.

2.2.3 User and Knowledge Ecologies

Within these co-creation environments, continuous mutual engagement and learning will occur along the whole implementation process between those developing and implementing the CPS4TIC and the different users that must work in or be treated in this environment. Using the metaphor of ecology tries to emphasise the continuous mutual adjustment of actors (Star, 1995) when coming together in the realm of an issue to be addressed – in our case the introduction or expansion of a CPS4TIC in the ICU Hubs. As a metaphor, "ecology" is meant to sensitize us to the spatial and temporal patterns of the distribution, in our case of different users and their knowledge, within each of and across the ICU Hubs, including forms of cooperation and competition. It points to the importance of how humans interact with – in our case – their socio-technical environment.

"User ecologies" points to the co-presence of different and well-defined types of stakeholders/users in the co-creation environment and draws our attention to the relations between people and technologies in the context of their operating environment. The user groups that will be at the core of the co-creation approach are medical doctors, nursing staff, other institutional actors but also patients and their families – the blend of users present will be depending on the situation we are looking at. In short, for each ICU of the future we will have to identify the user ecology, i.e. which users specifically come together, how they intersect, interact and how together they matter for the successful implementation process.

At the same time these users hold specific sets of knowledge, skills and experiences which would need to be considered when building a co-creation environment. When wanting to describe user knowledge ecologies in a given ICU Hub, we could take inspiration by Mäkinen and co-author's (2018) methodology of mapping knowledge ecologies, which is specifically attentive to "how organisations and project teams know their users, and how this knowing is intertwined in other organisational processes." This approach does not only draw attention to the multiplicity of forms of knowledge and experiences available in any environment, but also to the blending of informal and formal ways of mutually understanding users in real-life settings (Pollock & Williams, 2008; Oudshoorn & Pinch, 2003; Akrich 1995). This means that when implementing new technological capacities into the ICU Hubs it will be essential to tap into the pool of insights available from different sources.

Being attentive to the situated user and knowledge ecologies, we will thus have to put in place different formats, through which the consortium can collectively identify and prioritize the issues and concerns of different user groups and formalize them as user requirements in terms of desired elements and functionalities for the CPS4TIC, also reflecting how the different digital solutions come together in practice.

2.2.4 Versions of co-creation approaches

While the importance of this approach has been highlighted in multiple studies, it is for sure not a silver bullet and therefore the process needs to be developed and implemented very carefully and adapted to the challenges and objectives at hand.

When looking more closely into the different versions of co-creation approaches that have emerged over the years, Greenhalgh and co-authors (2016) identify four conceptualisations: (1) value co-creation, (2) community-based participatory research, (3) experience-based co-design and (4) technology co-design. These four understandings differ in focus and sensitivities, in the epistemological roots they are inspired by and, in turn, in the different key stakeholder groups that should be involved in the co-creation process (see also Felt, Öchsner & Rae, 2019b).

For developing co-creation environments in the ICU4Covid project, we will mainly take inspiration from two of these approaches, namely experience-based and value co-creation. Experience-based co-design is a frequently used approach in the field of healthcare service development “how well people understand it [e.g. a technology to be designed], how they feel and how well it fits into the context in which they are using it” (Bate & Robert, 2006, p. 309). We use the notion of co-creation instead of co-design – i.e. **evidence-based co-creation (EBCC)** – as we will engage with the implementation process rather than with the design of the implemented technologies as such – even though adaptations potentially might be needed on the technical level. This approach takes the diverse sets of experiences and forms of knowledge held by actors and users in the field as a starting point when re-assembling the ICU hubs. Experience-based co-creation thus focuses on users’ attitudes, experiences as well as knowledge and makes them accessible to those doing the technological implementation. This constitutes a unique and instrumental input to the co-creation process which is all too often neglected (Bate & Robert, 2006). In the case of ICU4Covid we will include all those that have to work within the re-assembled ICU Hubs. Methodologically, EBCC thus underlines that it is not sufficient to involve users in evaluating healthcare arrangements in the ICU Hub but privileges collaborative work of users and those developing and implementing the CPS4TIC in the ICU Hubs. Experience, however, often remains tacit and can best be accessed through users’ narratives; storytelling thus will be our privileged way of accessing how users make sense of change in the ICU environment. This means being attentive to “how they occur in conversations and in what way they are used” (Czarniawska, 2004).

Value co-creation is in its initial form grounded in the field of business and management (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004), where it is used quite widely focusing on the joint production of value by a company and its customer through involving the latter in both, the problem definition and the development of related solutions. In an extensive literature review on co-creation, Greenhalgh and co-authors characterize the “driving principle” in value co-creation as being based on the assumption that “people are naturally creative and seek to generate value for themselves and others” (Greenhalgh et al., 2016, p. 398). In the case of ICU4Covid, we have to fundamentally rethink this approach, asking the question how “value” is defined in the healthcare system, and more specifically in the ICU context, and whose values are potentially prioritized. In this context, it is essential to not start from

the assumption that value can be clearly defined from the start and progress measured against it, but what counts as value and how different values relate to each other will be the outcome of a combination of our engagements and emerging issues in the process. In this context, Dussauge and co-authors (2015) offer interesting insights into the multiplicity of understandings of the very notion of value when seen from the perspective of different subsystems or groups of actors. Indeed, we often differentiate and of “cultural” values, “medical” values or “economic” values, which points to the impossibility of abstractly defining what the very notion of value means. Thus, to understand which values matter, we have to dive deeper into a specific system and to understand how, when, why and for whom a specific technological innovation or a new practice becomes valuable, i.e. realises a specific value.

Borrowing from Grönroos et al. 2015), and differentiating between those responsible for the implementation and diverse user groups, we can distinguish four different types of value creation:

IMPLEMENTATION ACTORS	unaware	user driven value creation	value creation is situated and not necessarily very stable
	intentional	intentional engagement and collective value creation	those implementing drive the value creation
		intentional	unaware
USERS			

Table 3 - Types of value co-creation

This means that attention has to be given to those driving processes of value generation.

3 CURRENT DEBATES ON THE EU LEVEL

The last two decades have led to a fundamental shift in the relation of social life and the use of technologies through digitization. The use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) spread from specific contexts such as, scientific, military or administrative applications to more general contexts on a global scale. The transformation that was initiated by the digitization is still ongoing and its impacts are often not clear yet. What makes this current technological transformation distinct from others before is the fact that it affects every area of life in one way or the other – with healthcare being a central area of transformation through digital technologies. Such changes make legislative action necessary, especially when it comes to sensible areas like the personal health and the way healthcare practices are conducted. With the digitization the idea of electronic healthcare or eHealth became more and more important, but also new practices of medical treatment and care, such as telemedicine, could be imagined and established over time.

Current debates around the digitization of healthcare in the European Union are rooted in the *Europe 2020 Strategy* that was put forward by the European Commission in the light of the after-effects of the financial crisis of 2007/2008. A central idea of this strategy was to ‘bring Europe back on track’ and to make it more resistant to unprecedented situations. As a result of this strategic view technological innovations have gained in importance for the European Commission’s plans. In the context of digitization and in the light of attempts to create a unified European digital market, the *Digital Agenda for Europe* (DAE) was launched as one of the seven flagship initiatives of the Europe 2020 strategy in the same year. The goal of the DAE was “to maximize the social and economic potential of [ICTs]” (European Commission, 2010).

132 action items were defined to put the DAE in practice and assess its progress and status. Three of these action items are specifically targeting the topic of eHealth: *First*, Action 75, is targeted at the widespread deployment of telemedicine all over Europe. Previous projects funded by the EU, i.e. THALEA⁴ and THALEA II⁵, have been aligned with this action item and the ICU4Covid project also engages it. *Second*, Action 76, is about the definition of a common set of patient data that can be accessed and exchanged through shared patient record systems. This is especially important as local conditions and regulations for the healthcare sector are varying and only by creating common standards within the EU better exchange of knowledge and healthcare services is possible. Leading to the *third*, Action 77, that is about the creation of interoperability between eHealth systems and data sets across the EU. This is described as a prerequisite (European Commission, 2010) to offer qualitatively better and more cost-effective healthcare services to every citizen.

Just as important as the cost-effectiveness is for new technologies in the healthcare sector, they also pose ethical questions, especially those with potentially high socio-economic and human rights impacts. The EU-funded project SIENNA⁶ focused on this particular topic,

⁴ THALEA, Grant agreement ID 611855: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/611855>

⁵ THALEA II, Grant agreement ID 689041: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/689041>

⁶ SIENNA, Grant agreement ID 741716: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/741716>

engaging with different types of high-impact technologies and forms of application. The project combined the study of public opinions towards certain technologies with a review of the legal situation in the EU, as well as approaches for ethics-by-design.

With the expiration of the Europe 2020 strategy, the current European Commission of President Ursula von der Leyen has put forward six priorities for its period until 2024. One of these priorities is to make 'Europe fit for the digital age' which includes the promotion of digital innovations in different areas including that of healthcare. As she recently highlighted⁷, the 2020's should become 'Europe's 'Digital Decade''. To achieve this, specific funding is necessary, just as new regulations that open up opportunities for businesses and citizens in this digital decade.

As described at the beginning of this report the ongoing crisis has created widespread attention for the challenges of the healthcare sector, especially the ICUs. To strengthen these areas, the European Commission has specifically planned investments in digital technologies. At least 20% of the investments made through the NextGenerationEU framework⁸, which is an additional budget to the general Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF), will be made in the digital sphere⁶. For the immediate response to COVID-19 extra funding is redirected to researchers through a special call, that supports close-to-market technical solutions and the market innovation of existing solutions⁹. Here, thirteen projects currently receive funding from the European Commission, including ICU4Covid. This pool of projects includes among others projects that seek to improve the safe monitoring and treatment of patients in ICUs (ICU4Covid, ENVISION¹⁰, VASCOVID¹¹), others that are addressing the issue of determining whether a patient is infected with COVID-19 or not by using AI systems (icovid¹²), and projects that are working to prevent COVID-19 from spreading through aerosols through the use of new technical processes (PORSAB¹³, CleanAir¹⁴). Connecting to these projects, in particular the ICU related projects, will be important throughout the co-creation process to integrate also insights gained from these projects.

In the upcoming years, the European Commission is planning to put on the way two further pieces of legislation in response to digitization, its effects, challenges and risks. The first is the Digital Services Act (DSA) and the second is the Digital Markets Act (DMA)¹⁵. These new pieces of legislation are to bring more clarity and unity for the general conditions that all digital

⁷ Keynote speech by President von der Leyen at the 'Masters of Digital 2021' event on February 4, 2021: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/SPEECH_21_419

⁸ Recovery plan for Europe: https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/recovery-plan-europe_en

⁹ Medical technologies, Digital tools and Artificial Intelligence (AI) analytics to improve surveillance and care at high Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) (H2020_SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2B): https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2B

¹⁰ ENVISION, Grant agreement ID 101015930: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101015930>

¹¹ VASCOVID, Grant agreement ID 101016087: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101016087>

¹² icovid, Grant agreement ID 101016131: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101016131>

¹³ PORSAB, Grant agreement ID 101015941: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101015941>

¹⁴ CleanAir, Grant agreement ID 101016174: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101016174>

¹⁵ The Digital Services Act package: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/digital-services-act-package>

businesses and institutions in the European Union must and can act in. The impact of this upcoming legislation is currently difficult to assess.

The following sub-chapters offer an overview and summary of current debates at the European level about the topics at centre of the ICU4Covid project which include telemedicine (**chapter 3.1**), robotics in (health)care (**chapter 3.2**), and Artificial Intelligence in healthcare (**chapter 3.3**). This overview is based on various policy papers, proceedings from workshops with experts, as well as statements and suggestions from different European institutions. As these visions, discourses and decisions form together an important environment for the ICU4Covid project we will engage with some of its key elements.

3.1 Telemedicine and its preconditions

Not only since the outbreak of the global COVID-19 pandemic changes in the national and European healthcare infrastructure as well as the processes of healthcare services have been in the focus of EU executive and legislative bodies. As early as 1994 the European Commission has supported research that focused on establishing infrastructures for telemedical services to ship vessels and populations living in remote areas¹⁶. The efforts for improved healthcare services have persisted and in its strategic plan for the years 2016 to 2020 the Directorate General for Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE) of the European Commission underlined its commitment “for better public health and better access, effectiveness and resilience” for the healthcare systems of all EU Member States (DG Health & Food Safety, 2016, p. 4). The European Commission views telemedicine as an essential component for creating a more efficient and patient-oriented healthcare system across Europe. They especially highlight the advantages of implementing telemedical infrastructures for people in remote areas or those who are less mobile (DG Health & Food Safety, 2016).

In the context of EU legislation, telemedicine is regarded as a healthcare service and an information service at the same time (Raposo, 2016). This is important to consider as it means that regulations regarding healthcare practices as well as the data security and privacy regulations need to be met when storing, processing or transferring data related to patients’ health status. As this form of data, *health data* in the following, which includes the data produced, stored and transferred via telemedical infrastructures, enjoys particular protection under the General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR), special safeguard measures are necessary¹⁷. These measurements do not only require new technological standards, such as safe encryption for the storage and transfer of data, but also new ways of engagement for the medical professionals.

In 2018, the European Commission stated that the transformation of the European healthcare system needs financial investments. These investments should support the development and implementation of “digitally-enabled, person-centred care solutions” (European Commission, 2018a, p. 12). A digital approach to healthcare is thus seen as a suitable solution for the

¹⁶ NIVEMES, Grant agreement ID HC1035: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/HC1035>

¹⁷ Health | European Data Protection Supervisor: https://edps.europa.eu/data-protection/our-work/subjects/health_en

challenges that healthcare systems encounter, aiming at making them more efficient and accessible for everyone while also empowering patients to make their choices. To achieve financial efficiency of these investments, the European Commission sees scalability of technological solutions as a central condition. According to a market study on telemedicine published by the European Commission in 2018 the market potential for such technologies in Europe is strong, thus even before the current pandemic was a matter of concern (European Commission, 2018b).

Even though the general idea of telemedicine, that is the remote provision of healthcare services, is not new, digitization brings new opportunities for its specific arrangement. Before the emergence of widespread ICTs, telemedical practices have been conducted via telephone and thus only allowed for verbal communication between the medical professionals and the patients. Digital technologies today enable new approaches to the idea of telemedicine, i.e. the sharing of videos as well as patient records in real-time.

The market study concludes another important point in the context of telemedicine. As of now, most of the existing standards and regulations surrounding telemedicine refer to its *technical* aspects. As a result of the DAE these technical standards have been developed and are already in a status of technical maturity. Having said this the European Commission is aware that the existing “inadequate IT infrastructure” hinders the implementation of new telemedical systems across Europe (European Commission, 2018b, p. 127). In the last years, different projects have hence been funded with the goal of closing the technological gap between what is theoretically possible and practically implemented. The THALEA project¹⁸ for example successfully implemented telemonitoring infrastructures between 2013 and 2016 in different European regions. Especially the development of standardized technological solutions that can help with the integration of different medical providers, such as hospitals, can be seen as a success of this project. The follow-up project THALEA II¹⁹ deepened this approach and focused in addition on the procurement aspect to push the widespread deployment of telemedicine in the EU. The idea of a public procurement of innovative solutions (PPI) should enable public bodies to make better procurement decisions and also bundle existing efforts to utilize the single digital market in Europe.

While the technical standards have been developed, but are not yet put in practice everywhere, the *socio-cultural* implications of such a fundamental change to the way healthcare is practiced across different sites is essential. The European Commission (2018b) therefore also highlights in their market study that it is important to take a look at the actual needs of medical professionals and patients. If these stakeholders are not considered and included in a process of co-creation (see also **chapter 2**) the implementation of any new technology in the healthcare sector is at risk to fail in practice. That’s why the European Commission requires special attention to the social aspects and implications of new technological solutions in the area of healthcare.

¹⁸ THALEA, Grant agreement ID 611855: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/611855>

¹⁹ THALEA II, Grant agreement ID 689041: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/689041>

3.2 Robotics as answer to changing demographics

The care work that is done in ICUs is important and at the same time faces somewhat different challenges compared to other contexts where care is practiced. The fact that patients might be more vulnerable to infectious diseases make the use of robotics an appealing approach. Such technological solutions could be part of an approach that allows medical professionals to provide high quality healthcare services while at the same time keeping everyone safe.

Historically, the use of robotics has a long-standing tradition in industrial production, not only since the broad discussion around Industry 4.0 emerged. Robotic technologies are able to perform *specific tasks* quicker and more accurately than humans and they are also able to perform tasks that might be dangerous for and potentially harmful to human workers. The European Commission is closely monitoring the development and usage of robotics in different areas. Here, the focus is primarily on the opportunities that robotics can bring to the economic competitiveness of European businesses and how they can be combined with digital technologies, i.e. Artificial Intelligence (European Commission, 2020).

Within the Horizon 2020 framework the European Commission established the Public Private Partnership in Robotics (PPP), a group consisting of members of the 'European robotics industry, research and academia'²⁰. The goal of the PPP is to establish a shared roadmap for the development of robotics in the EU and to discuss which conditions need to be established to realize it. The role of the European Commission in this group is to provide the platform and to use the outcomes of the PPP for their own funding and legislation strategies. By now, the PPP is focusing more on the interrelation of the topics robotics, AI and data in order to find 'a common ground' for them (euRobotics, 2020). This relates to an important aspect in the context of digitization: Different technological and social developments do overlap and thus also need to be considered in a joint way.

In a conference, hosted by the European Parliament, on 'Robots in Healthcare: a solution or a problem?', the question of the demand of such robotic support was also discussed. Kathrin Cresswell explained that a "negative attitude and concerns from the public, patients and healthcare staff appear to be contributing to a lack of demand and acceptance for some robotic applications in healthcare settings." (European Parliament, 2019, p. 12)

Thereby we have to consider the level of automation and the tasks that are performed by robotics in order to determine which ethical and legal considerations should be made (European Parliament, 2016). As in the case of ICU4Covid robotics can merely be used as assistive technologies that on the one side support the nursing staff in their everyday work and on the other side to reducing the risk of infections. While robotics and their (possible) applications are widely discussed on the EU level, there is currently no specific and consistent regulation in place regarding its use and questions of accountability.

The use of bedside 'robotic arms' that can support the medical professionals and the nursing staff in stabilizing or moving patients, is currently not part of any legal regulations. To create a

²⁰ Robotics Public-Private Partnership in Horizon 2020: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/robotics-public-private-partnership-horizon-2020>

successful and scalable solution legal certainty is important and required, for the patients, but also the medical professionals.

3.3 A European strategy on Artificial Intelligence

The topic of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has received great attention throughout the last years. This is especially the case in areas where large amounts of data, often called "Big Data", are produced and processed. While the first stage of digitization was mainly focused on the transformation from analogue to ICT-based systems of storing and processing information, the increasing interconnection of these data silos has been at the centre of recent efforts. Today, data it is no longer just about the information that are explicitly collected and stored, but about the information that can be generated based on such data sets (see **chapter 4.2** for more). In particular the prediction of future developments is a central vision for the use of AI in various areas.

Besides its potential the increased use of AI also poses questions and challenges, especially from the point of view of transparency and equality. To address these pressing challenges new European regulations are not only necessary but can bring an advantage to the development and usage of AI.

In 2018 the European Commission introduced a new approach and push towards the development and use of systems that incorporate AI (European Commission, 2018c). AI and its various fields of applications - such as healthcare, the fight against climate change or the anticipation of cybersecurity threats - are positioned as the solution for the pressing issues of our time that affect the lives of all European citizens. That is why the European Commission is pushing for 'an EU initiative on AI'. Besides tackling the mentioned issues, such an initiative should bring new jobs and business opportunities to the EU Members States.

A central challenge for the European Commission is to coordinate the efforts on AI between all Member States. To achieve this, they have put forward a Coordination Plan in 2018 that includes the proposition for 70 joint actions regarding research, investment, market uptake, and more. Through the coordination investments to AI should be made more efficiently compared to the individual actions every Member State can make. The expected investments that should be collected through this coordinated approach is valued to be around 20 billion € per year (European Commission, 2020).

As a recent white paper proposes the topic of AI should especially be used to engage with current societal challenges, thereby specifically taking into account societal and environmental aspects of new technological innovations (European Commission, 2020). The European Commission is aware that trust is a central factor if innovations in AI are to be taken up by European societies more broadly. As users and consumers of AI systems all European citizens should be able to rely on a common framework of regulation for AI.

The European Commission identifies three areas of beneficiaries for the use of AI: (1) the citizens that receive benefits through better products and services; (2) businesses that can realize new opportunities; and (3) the public interest as a reduction of cost and/or better usage

of existing resources is possible. Only by creating benefits for these three areas AI is expected to be successful. This goal is to be achieved by creating innovative technological solutions through the coordination of already existing efforts of research institutions or private companies. Also, the stimulation of new innovations is central for Europe's AI strategy. Ultimately the declared aim is to "become a global leader in innovation in the data economy and its applications." (European Commission, 2020, p. 2)

While wanting to advance in this direction, there is also a growing awareness that the use of AI brings new challenges that need to be addressed. Overall, it is described as important that "European AI is grounded in our values and fundamental rights such as human dignity and privacy protection." (European Commission, 2020, p. 2) The strength of a coordinated European approach is thus perceived in its capability to connect technological innovations with European values. Besides the Coordination Plan between the Member's States, the European Commission also co-founded 'the European AI Alliance', a multi-stakeholder platform that should develop and discuss the specific orientation of a European AI strategy. The platform is comprised of different stakeholders from private companies, research institutions as well as political bodies. Once again, the European Commission takes the role of enabling discussions between these different partners to ultimately get insights about important legislative steps that support European efforts on AI²¹. As discussed earlier, the euRobotics (2020) consortium is also engaging with the topic of AI, in connection with its application to robotics.

To address the ethical, legal and social challenges that are connected with the development, implementation and usage of AI, concrete methods are necessary in each of these phases. The SIENNA project²² not only developed a framework that identifies the actors to involve in such processes, but also created corresponding methods that can be used in any project that seeks to develop new technologies. In this context, they further highlight the importance of 'motivating' all actors to engage with the ethical, legal and social challenges that come with their own work (SIENNA, 2020).

At the same time that AI and its applications are discussed broadly throughout the EU, the dimension of data plays an important role in digitization as well. As Ursula von der Leyen highlighted in a recent talk, "Data needs to be shared and exchanged more widely."²³ As the current lack of regulation in the area of AI is not suitable for upcoming digital innovations, according to her, the European Commission will present a detailed legal framework for AI in Europe as well as a Data Act and specific proposals on Health Data Spaces. These pieces of legislation should, on the one side, foster trust in digital technologies including AI by the citizens and on the other side create certainty for companies working on such technologies.

With the coming into effect of the European GDPR regulation, data produced and used in the context of health has received stronger protection. A uniform regulation on the storage and processing of health data can be a chance for the challenges that the European healthcare

²¹ The European AI Alliance: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/european-ai-alliance>

²² SIENNA, Grant agreement ID 741716: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/741716>

²³ Keynote speech by President von der Leyen at the 'Masters of Digital 2021' event on February 4, 2021 (~11:40): https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/SPEECH_21_419

systems are facing. A cooperation between core and peripheral hospitals, the exchange of knowledge and expertise, can be done across borders if necessary. To do so the legal requirements and the understandings of these requirements need to be aligned. In a recent report on the 'Assessment of the EU Member States' rules on health data in the light of GDPR' published by the DG Food and Health Safety (2021), the authors make clear that this is currently still a problem. Especially the navigation of the GDPR and local implementations is difficult for medical institutions and professionals, researchers and patients.

The study concludes that even though different groups of stakeholders are in favour of a 'European Health Data Space', so a shared online space for the storage and processing of health data, but that the current legal situation and its implementation creates scepticism for its practical feasibility. This feasibility could be strengthened, according to the authors, by creating technical standards for the sharing of health data that ensures the interoperability between systems, institutions and countries, and by building more trust in data governance practices and measurements of the European Union (DG Health and Food Safety, 2021).

With its potential to recognize patterns in larger data sets the use of AI in the healthcare sector is a promising endeavour. That is why various private companies and research institutions have started to develop technological solutions based on or around the existing data infrastructures of healthcare providers. Thereby specific challenges have to be mastered, especially when it comes to the storage, processing and transfer of health data as defined by the European Commission. The Smart4Health project²⁴ is for example addressing some of these challenges. While the processing of data might be beneficial to individual patients or patients in general through the use of health data for medical research, patients still have to be in charge of the decision if their data is automatically processed or shared.

²⁴ Grant agreement ID: 826117 | <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/826117>

4 REFLECTING TECHNOLOGICAL IMPLEMENTATIONS

The technological innovations that are at the core of the ICU4Covid project are mainly centred around telemedical care (and all related digital technologies), data driven patient surveillance and decision support systems as well as robotics (with a focus on a robotic arm to support bedside care). In this chapter we bring together the key lines of discussions in the social sciences (with a specific focus on science and technology studies literature) that have developed around these innovations and their potential impacts. Together they form a background for reflecting on the implementation process.

4.1 Telemedical systems and their challenges

Research into telemedicine deploying SSH frameworks as the one we have outlined in **chapter 2** is premised by **two basic assumptions**. The *first* states that it does not suffice to view telemedicine only from a medical, technological or economic perspective because then such research is in danger of not “getting the whole picture” (Halford et al., 2010; Berg, 2001). Conceiving the ICU as a socio-technical assemblage as we have outlined in **chapter 2.2.2** counteracts this danger by focusing on the heterogeneous components that constitute the assemblage – human actors, technologies, institutional/organizational actors, etc. – and the relations forged between them. Moreover, taking a Responsible Innovation-informed co-creation approach from the outset further mitigates potential shortcomings by acknowledging and considering the social and societal dimension of any innovation.

The *second*, related premise that underlies research into telemedicine in SSH is that “technologies are never neutral but should be considered as active transformers of health care” (Oudshoorn, 2009, p. 391; Pols, 2012). This assumption highlights the role technologies play in the socio-technical assemblages of the ICU. Adding a new technical component to an existing assemblage shifts the relationships between *all* of its components – this is why we talk about re-assembling the ICU. Adding the technologies that connect the peripheral ICUs with the ICU Hub, putting in place data driven decision support systems and bringing robotics arms to ICU bedsides does not only add a (further) technological dimension to healthcare practices but also changes how they can be performed in everyday contexts. Starting from these assumptions, research into telemedicine has developed in different strands, each highlighting varying dimensions: the relationship between telemedical systems and established clinical routines and identities; the important role space and place play in telemedical systems and, finally, an emerging body of research about telemedicine during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Discrepancies between theories of use and actual practices

To start with, the relationship between telemedicine and established routines and practices in the healthcare sector has been a fruitful avenue of research. When developing technologies, designers have a “theory of use” (Lehoux et al., 2002) which includes assumptions about the future user and the future contexts of use that inform the design of the socio-technical artifact. Consequentially, the successful and sustainable implementation of the technology hinges on how well these design assumptions about the use and its context fit the actual use context or

how adaptable the technology is for environments that do not match the assumptions they incorporate (Akrich, 1992). To this end, several scholars have pointed out the mismatches between the design of telemedical technologies and their use related to the projected clinical needs, the trust in (digitally) transmitted information (Lehoux et al., 2002) and the logic of contextualized, non-formalizable, holistic medical practice and knowledge (Kamp & Hansen, 2019; Hanlon et al., 2005). Deborah Lupton and Sarah Maslen (2017, p. 1564) contrast telemedicine and existing clinical practices with respect to what they call “sensory work” and, thus, add an important dimension to the ICU4Covid project. They ask how the introduction of new technological means changes what we know – i.e. what we can sense – about the status of a patient and therefore pose the question of which information count when making decisions concerning treatment. In this context, we could also refer to Harris (2021) who argues for a need to be attentive to sensory engagements and learning in the medical field, in particular in data intense environments. These insights stress the need for our project to be attentive to the *existing* socio-technical assemblages the CPS4TIC is imported into and how this relates to routines, experiences and practices. Again, the SSH-informed co-creation approach will serve to bridge the gap between implementers and users of the technology.

Shifting (occupational) identities of the users

Designers do not only make assumptions about where and how, but also by whom their technology will be used. This process – that we refer to as “enrolment”, the attribution of a role within the socio-technical assemblage – has profound implications for the (occupational) identities of the users. As the ICU is re-assembled, what it means to be a patient, a physician or a nurse is re-defined and new occupational roles, for instance, personnel staffing the ICU Hubs and monitoring patients’ conditions from afar, as well as relations between them will be created (Kamp & Hansen, 2019; Mort et al., 2009; Nicolini, 2007; 2006; Mort et al., 2003). Mort and her colleagues (2009) provide an important addition to these contributions and to the project: They argue that it does not suffice to reduce participants to their (occupational) role within the healthcare sector – receiver or provider – and that, instead, their position as citizens within larger socio-political contexts needs to be considered. As the introduction of telemedical system also relates to broader societal dimensions, the project needs to establish continuous feedback loops with both local, national and supranational political institutions as well as the publics at these different levels. As part of the re-definition of occupational identities, new concepts of what it means to provide care will emerge, forcing personnel to give up and/or modify their previous understandings and practices of healthcare (Samuellson & Berner, 2013). Finally, along with the occupational identities of those working in healthcare and their understandings of their occupation, the identities of organizations shift when a new technology that cuts across, such as telemedicine, is implemented (Hendy & et al., 2014), e.g. the definitions of a hospital as central/peripheral within the socio-technical assemblage. Research has shown that the redefinitions of occupational and organizational identities and understandings of healthcare practices bear considerable potential for conflict that the project will have to be sensitive for in order to ensure a successful implementation and scalability of CPS4TIC. Hence, providing a narrative that allows users and participating organizations to link their previously held identities with those that emerge during the implementation stages and beyond will be crucial. In other words: “people need[,] something new and bold to believe in” (Hendy et al.,

2014, p. 441). SSH-research has shown that such narratives emerge during “fateful events” (Giddens, 1992) – such as the COVID-19 pandemic – but are, more importantly, facilitated by and within socio-technical assemblages (Oudshoorn, 2008).

Additional work of integrating the technology is necessary

A number of the referenced contributions suggest that telemedicine systems do not automatically and smoothly integrate into existing systems of care. On the contrary, potentially they can disrupt them, making additional work of integrating the technology necessary. This is a crucial theme for our project as re-assembling the ICU entails re-distributing work to human and delegating some of it to technologies. This re-distribution, in turn, necessitates new ways of coordinating the distributed labour, the invisible, unforeseen but nonetheless necessary “work to make telemedicine work” (Nicolini, 2006). The work necessary to coordinate telemedical systems, Nelly Oudshoorn (2008) argues, usually remains invisible as it is not anticipated by implementers. It includes the development of the necessary skills to use the technology, including the skills of repairing them ad-hoc, the explanatory work necessary to re-assure patients and their relatives about the technology, the labour necessary to compensate for the distance that is introduced into clinical practice (e.g. selecting appropriate information to communicate with the remote physicians) and the additional work to integrate new distribution of labour with existing regulatory frameworks (i.e. questions of accountability and responsibility in case of miscommunication or disagreements) (Kamp & Hansen, 2019; Samuelsson & Berner, 2013; Pappas & Seale, 2009; Oudshoorn, 2008, 2012; Nicolini, 2006, 2007; Tanriverdi & Iacono, 1999). Despite remaining invisible and unacknowledged, this work is crucial as “it constitutes one of the critical factors towards the success of any technological innovation” (Nicolini, 2006, p. 2759). The SSH-framework that we have developed here is attuned to new, invisible and unforeseen types of work that the implementation of CPS4TIC into clinical practice necessitates and, hence, is decisive for making it visible and accountable as part of the ICU4Covid project and beyond.

Importance of the locality

Telemedicine has been associated with the ability to eradicate the constraints posed by space and time in the provision of healthcare services (e.g. by connecting remote areas without sufficient healthcare provisions with hospitals in urban regions). Many scholars working with SSH-frameworks have challenged this assumption, highlighting the importance of the locality of the site where telemedical systems are implemented: The success of the latter hinges to a large part on how they are integrated into the local ways of providing and understanding care, local administrative, organizational or regulatory arrangements as well as local identities and relationships between patients, physicians and nursing staff, among others (Grisot et al., 2019; Samuelsson & Berner, 2013; Petersson, 2011; Dyb & Halford, 2009; Oudshoorn, 2008, 2012; Miscione, 2007; Collin-Jacques & Smith, 2005; Lehoux et al., 2002;). These findings align with the concept of 'socio-cultural interoperability' outlined above (**chapter 2.2.1**): It sensitizes us for the specific local contexts the technology becomes a part of and how they inflect its use. The comparative approach we have proposed serves to follow and contrast the different practices of “localization” (Samuelsson & Berner, 2013; Berg, 1997), i.e. the ways how the technology is adapted to the specific contexts. Another line of research in this vein, has investigated how telemedicine re-configures the spatial relationship between the components

of the socio-technical assemblages. Thus, for example, telemedicine may be a part of broader institutional mergers of regions or facilitate future collaborations between the hospitals it has connected (Pettersson, 2011; 2016). The relationship between centre and periphery in this respect has sparked a rather controversial discussion. Some authors warn of a geographical and economic gap that is being reinforced; a gap between the regions considered as “periphery” or “center” (Nicolini, 2006; Cartwright, 2001; Bareiss, 2001) as well as between established “big players” and actors with less financial resources (Nicolini, 2006). Others have ascertained that the connections have led to a strengthening of the periphery (Kamp & Hansen, 2019). This discussion calls the project to be attentive to how it affects the relationship both in a short- and long-term perspective.

Telemedicine during the COVID-19 pandemic

Finally, as of yet, a small body of literature has probed into the possible implications of telemedicine in tackling the COVID-19 pandemic (Eaves et al., 2020; Milne & Costa, 2020). Although this research is, naturally, rather tentative in assessing this relationship, it highlights the need to consider the COVID-19 and its transmission as a participant in the socio-technical assemblage with the ability to rapidly shift around relations and possibilities. In this respect, research from medical disciplines into implementations of (improvised) telemedical systems has focused on the attitudes of epileptologists using these systems (Conde-Blanco et al., 2020) and the relationship of the use of telemedical systems and the occurrence of complications in fracture clinics (Smith et al., 2020). However, neither did these studies analyse pre-planned and extensive implementations such as CPS4TIC, nor did they explicitly acknowledge the entanglements we refer to with the concept of socio-technical assemblage (although they already refer us to the relationship between regulations, such as lockdown regulations, the transmissibility of COVID-19 and the affordances of different devices used for telemedical consultations).

4.2 Knowing with/through Data

With the growing relevance of ICT and the related trends towards digitization, issues surrounding data have sparked considerable research interest in SSH. For a project that proposes the introduction of a telemedicine system that transmits health data in various forms and using different technologies back-and-forth between peripheral ICUs and an ICU Hub in the center, research into what has recently been called the 'datafication of health' (Ruckenstein & Schüll, 2017) becomes especially pertinent. This research looks into the broader context this tendency belongs to and how it re-defines concepts of the body and the new practices vis-à-vis data and the body.

Datafication of health brings a broader shift in medical thought and practice

The “datafication of health” can be linked to a broader shift in medical thought and practice that emerged slowly throughout the 20th century and has gained further traction with the large-scale implementation of ICT in the healthcare sector. This new medical paradigm shifts attention from individual population data and the (AI-enhanced) identification of disease and risk probabilities (Reubi, 2018; Nettleton, 2004; Armstrong, 1995). In particular, the biomedical understanding of the body changes in the course of the shift as it is conceived of as a producer,

processor and carrier of information. Accordingly, this information may be extracted and re-assembled as a “data body” (Mager & Mayer, 2019) or a “data double” (Matzner, 2016; Lupton, 2015; Lyon, 2003; Haggerty & Ericson, 2000; see also Deleuze, 1992). The body, in other words, is “e-escaped in the sense that it is ‘viewable’ through the electronic info-scape that is the internet” (Nettleton, 2004, p. 670; see also Webster, 2002). To conceptualize the production of digital (bodily) data, scholars like Tommaso Venturini et al. (2017) draw on the longstanding concept of “inscription devices” (Latour, 2003; Latour & Woolgar, 1986). Inscription devices are apparatuses that produce partial representations, for example, of the body by extracting some of the information and translating it into a different form such as fever curves or, in the context of ICT, sequences of zeroes and ones. Either way, the devices produce only one of many possible representations of the body (Mol, 2002). Hence, equipped with these insights, the project will be attentive of the capacity of the technological devices in the socio-technical assemblage to extract and translate data from the body and how these are re-assembled to constitute the body of the patient that may then be transmitted back-and-forth between sites – but so, too, will we be able to consider how this particular understanding of the body co-exists and or/conflicts with other understandings in the context of care.

Data is not self-evident – it is composed by actors

Research into data in SSH has challenged naive understandings of data as simply and self-evidently given – as implied by the etymology of the word – and instead emphasized that data is always produced within “complex sociotechnical assemblages” (Kitchin, 2014, p. 24) or “information infrastructures” (Bowker et al., 2010). Their components and the relationship between them simultaneously enable and constrain the collection of data, what is considered as “data” in a given context and at different sites within the assemblages, how data is expected to function in these contexts and how data may travel within and between them (Fiore-Gartland & Neff, 2015; Neff, 2013; Coopmans, 2006). The “data journeys” (Bates et al., 2016) occurring throughout the data assemblages/information infrastructures may occur at different speeds and with different modalities, depending on the composition of the assemblage and the relationship between them. They may experience “data friction” (Bates et al., 2016), i.e. blockages that stall their movement completely and/or force them to take a different shape, that may be caused by any of the actors (humans, technologies, etc.), although researchers have pointed out the crucial role politics and legislation, such as privacy concerns, may play in data frictions (Aula, 2019; Bates, 2018). These insights add an important dimension to how we may conceptualize the socio-technical assemblage that the ICU4Covid project seeks to create by bringing to the fore the crucial infrastructures that make data transmissions, and thus operating the telemedical system, possible in the first place and that are usually considered invisible, ready-to-hand (Star & Ruhleder, 1996). In particular, they point not only to additional components that need to be added our understanding of the socio-technical devices – the inscription devices that produce representations of specific bodily data and these representations themselves – but to the relations that connect the components and the different sites of the project. They offer vantage points for understanding how data may travel and what possible hindrances are.

Data work – diverse and intense

Finally, SSH scholars have highlighted the different types of work that data necessitate: Knowing through and with data takes skills and expertise – something that euphoric discourses about the promises of data tend to obliterate (Neff et al., 2017; Nadim, 2016; Bastard et al., 2013). Because “data assemblages” shape what can be gathered, stored and transmitted as data, the processes of designing and implementing them takes centre stage in the discussions. Authors put forward participatory design – such as the co-creation approach we want to pursue – in order to produce a democratic environment where different perspectives on data, “data valences” (Fiore-Gartland & Neff, 2015), held by different actors as well as the capabilities of socio-technical devices can enter a conversation about the needs and objectives of the data infrastructure. The requirement to coordinate different temporalities – such as, the short-order of the ICU4Covid project; the heterochronous rhythms of organizational, administrative, regulatory and technological turnover; the different speeds of training and passing on of skills and the long-term projection of a technological system designed to resolve the difficulties faced by national healthcare systems not only in times of crisis – imposes itself as especially pertinent in the process (Bowker et al., 2010).

“Data communicate” as Stine Lomborg et al. (2020) argue. That is, they offer “semiotic cues” that need to be interpreted by drawing on “personal and socio-culturally constituted resources to interpret them vis-à-vis the context they are embedded in” (p. 3). Interpreting data thus can be considered a skilful attempt of relating them to their origin within a socio-technical assemblage (Gray et al., 2018) and to prior experiences and expertise (Even Chorev, 2019; Grisot et al. 2019). In telemedical systems especially, where the transmission of (bodily) data becomes a primary source of information, such “data work” becomes crucial. In these cases it “is not only about analyzing the data elements accumulated in the system but also includes the work of deciding what is relevant data, and discerning which incoming data signal a follow up action for each specific patient” (Grisot et al., 2019, p. 615). Research into the relationship between the human body and data extracted from it – “human-data assemblages” (Lupton, 2018; Lupton, 2016) – has highlighted how in such practices of making sense of data, the understanding of the body is fundamentally shaped by these data (Lupton, 2018). In other words, we will need to consider how a patient’s body comes to be understood, e.g. as acutely in danger, as recovering, as healthy, within the practices of interpreting the health data extracted from and transmitted within the telemedicine systems, but also how nursing staff and physicians come to understand themselves and their roles in knowing with/through data. The “daily roundings” between staff at the ICU Hub and within the peripheral hospitals will be one of the sites where we will be able to follow the processes of collaborative data sense-making between physicians and the trajectories of patients’ data bodies/data doubles.

Dysfunctional moments

Finally, in the course of a recent shift in thinking about data in SSH, research has focused not only on the production and circulation of data but on breakdowns/disruptions and “broken data” (Pink et al., 2016) (as already evidenced by the concept of “data friction” referred to above). It illuminates the types of work necessary to fix breakdowns of both data collections (Pink et al., 2016) and data assemblages/infrastructures (Bowker et al., 2010) but also the new skills that need to be developed in detecting data errors (Garnett, 2016) and making sense of broken data (Pink et al., 2016; Schwennesen, 2019). These insights “suggest that repair work

and maintenance are part and parcel of our mundane living with data” (Lomborg et al., 2020, p. 3). For ICU4Covid, they add a layer of complexity as they call to appreciate the new occupational roles, skills and types of work that emerge and need to be guaranteed as part of the data infrastructure created between participant hospitals. Two possible examples in this case are those assigned the work of maintaining and repairing the information infrastructure or the skills of interpreting patient data from afar or algorithmic outputs in order to make decisions based on them. However, they also call for a consideration of the ethical/legal ramifications vis-à-vis the breakdown of critical infrastructure, such as the distribution of responsibilities.

4.3 Acting with/on Data: AI-Driven Decision-Support Systems

Besides any legal dimensions, the possibilities to use algorithms to support decision making in the ICU context is increasingly discussed also from an SSH perspective. However, while the majority of the latter studies engages with ethical dimensions of the issue at stake and identifies some of the crucial concerns to be attentive to (e.g. Braun et al., 2020; Grote & Berens, 2020; Hagendorff, 2020; Rességuier & Rodrigues 2020; Mittelstadt, 2019; Mittelstadt et al., 2016), much less is known so far on the impact of algorithms to support decision making in concrete work practices (some notable exceptions are Bailey et al., 2020; Even Chorev, 2019; Schwennesen, 2019; Pope et al., 2013). Indeed, the big challenge that lies ahead is to build AI driven decision support systems (AIDSS) which actually raise the quality of decision making and allow medical doctors, nursing staff and patients to keep the sovereign position. However, as has been underlined, the current pace of development, does carry the danger of not having a sufficiently fine-grained discussion about the values embedded in such systems, what new kinds of capacities they would demand from healthcare professionals in their communication among themselves and with patients and the level of digital literacy one would presuppose. Another question that remains unresolved for now is the distribution of (legal) responsibilities and accountabilities when AIDSS are implemented. Braun and co-authors (2020) have brought some of these challenges to the point by, in particular, pointing to the shift in conditions of trustworthiness, epistemic challenges regarding transparency, conclusiveness of evidence and the possibility of biases, alterations in the underlying concepts of agency, and finally the consequences for (possible) ascriptions of responsibility.

The trustworthiness of algorithms

Trustworthiness has been an issue present in many reflections on AIDSS, highlighting the importance of the interpersonal interactions in the medical field, both within the groups of health care professionals as well as between doctors and patients (EGE, 2018; Castell et al., 2017). Yet, we also encounter reflections on the complexity of grasping a relational concept like trust, and the need to more profoundly engage on what ground trust relations emerge and how technological means actually become trustworthy in the users’ eyes (e.g. Gille et al., 2020; Ostherr et al., 2017). In fact, trusting AI would mean to include the whole set of actors engaged in the process of data generation, data curation and integration that underpins a well-functioning AIDSS system. This then is not a question to be answered in abstract terms, but successful implementation demands a quite fine-grained understanding of how the different

actors that are expected to be supported by these systems perceive their trustworthiness. In a very recent article, Rikke Torenholt and Henriette Langstrup (2021) remind us that “trust” and the closely related notion of legitimacy of AIDSS are multifarious concepts that can take on different meanings at different levels, e.g. they show that the legitimacy of an AIDSS in the context of Danish healthcare takes a very different form on the political level than on the level of local physicians. Moreover, on any of these levels legitimacy may be based on what the authors call a “logic of disruption” — algorithms as a necessary transformation of medical practices — or on a “logic of continuation” — the extension of existing medical practices and, thus, existing forms of trust — that are continuously negotiated. At any rate, their insights point to the necessity of being well aware of the dynamics and tensions underlying trust and legitimacy in order to establish trusting relationships in the everyday encounters of doctors, patients and algorithms.

Epistemic challenges of algorithms: evidence, transparency, bias

“Epistemic challenges” in the context of algorithms refers to three interlinked issues that arise with the use of algorithms (Mittelstadt et al., 2016). The *first* refers to what counts as “evidence” in algorithms: Algorithms are designed to produce “actionable insights” (Mittelstadt et al., 2016, p. 4), i.e. sufficient evidence for subsequent medical interventions. This evidence, however, rests on a logic of probability and correlation rather than causation, as algorithms easily identify patterns within large sets of data but cannot account for underlying causal relations. Furthermore, underlying the actionable insights suggested by algorithms is a tension between the individual and the population. While patterns are derived from the population level, their validity for the given individual whose data are analysed in the AIDSS system can potentially open questions. The danger that AIDSS, thus, bear is that – in the worst case – they produce “[i]nconclusive evidence leading to unjustified action” (p. 4).

The *second* issue is that of transparency. It addresses the challenge clinical work is always confronted with, namely taking decisions under complex conditions, with little evidence and under pressure. While there is a clear promise in AIDSS to improve the speed of handling data and delivering insights, this also makes it hard for those taking the final decision to assess the basis on which AI has delivered the respective recommendation. Therefore, much of the process leading up to the recommendation gets black boxed; and even if it would be accessible, it can be hardly understood by many of those who either use the support system or are patients treated on the basis of such an AIDSS. This has been more specifically addressed in the by now extensive discussions around explainable algorithms, which points to the need that users should have the ability to understand and assess the mechanism intrinsic to an algorithm or a computational process in human terms.

The *third* epistemic challenge of algorithms discussed in the literature is that of input quality and bias. Algorithm-based decision-making depends on the quality of data that constitutes its “ground truth”, i.e. the data that is used to train the algorithm. The discussions on “data assemblages” and “information infrastructures” we have pointed to above (**chapter 4.2**) has shown that this input data is never simply given and neutral. Human actors have to make choices in the production and the interpretation of data that gets fed into the algorithm (see also Kotliar, 2021; Henriksen & Bechmann, 2020). Accordingly, algorithms incorporate or reflect

existing (tacit) social biases and, hence, “inevitably make biased decisions” (Mittelstadt et al., 2016, p. 7). This calls for a greater awareness for the origins of the algorithmic database and the practices that constitute the algorithm. This is all the more crucial in the context of healthcare where a possibly biased algorithm-based decision-making may have profound consequences.

Distributed agency and (al-)locating responsibility

These three epistemic issues, thus, further open the issue of agency and how it gets shared in new ways. In practice, the decision in the ICU depends already on a number of actors who are connected with the treatment of a patient, such as different medical specialists and care personnel – Nicolini (2007, p. 900) calls this “distributed cognition”. In a recent online article, Anna Harris and Lisa Herzog ask the provocative question “Could algorithms and artificial intelligence replace doctors and nurses as diagnostic experts?”²⁵ In their treatment of the questions, they argue that “training to be a doctor or nurse isn’t just about the acquisition of data points or building a human textbook of facts. It’s also an exercise in sensory and emotional attunement”. They, as already pointed to above, speak to the importance of the art of noticing, which means “a full sensory engagement with the sounds, images, feeling and general atmosphere of an encounter,” skills which are different to those performed through algorithmic pattern recognition (see also Maslen, 2016). We thus have to carefully reflect what role data-driven support systems play in the overall decision-making practice, how it impacts distributed cognition and what it will mean in terms of responsibilities. Algorithms, for sure, outperform humans in quickly recognizing patterns. Yet at the same time, algorithms are, on the one hand, rooted in specific models of the human body and health as well as on models of human diversity which evidently have potential blind spots, in particular not integrating more qualitative insights that medical professional capture, sometime tacitly, sometimes explicitly. On the other hand, as with any type of data-processing, “the output can never exceed the input” (Mittelstadt et al., 2016, p. 4). The quality of AI-based decision-making, thus, hinges on the quality of data produced by the medical inscription devices deployed in the ICU. While there is debate to create algorithms that include some of these concerns, there are also clear warnings that the solution might not be on the technical level, but needs both transparency of the model behind the algorithm as well as admitting the clear limits of data-driven decision making (e.g. McCradden et al., 2020).

Finally, the issue around agency leads automatically to the consequences the introduction of AIDSS for the explicit or implicit ascriptions of responsibility. At stake here is the “traceability” (Mittelstadt et al. 2016, p. 5) of decisions: Who makes a decision to act upon on what grounds and may be held responsible in case of harmful effects? This question needs to be addressed from several perspectives. We have to ask if there might not be a tendency to deferring decisions to the algorithm as this might provide a techno-normative justification (Grote & Berens, 2020). If a medical professional decides against the suggestion by the algorithm there is a certain danger that in case of problems this might be judged as irresponsible behaviour. Furthermore, the authors also underline that algorithmic suggestions might lead to a bias in

²⁵ Article by Anna Harris and Lisa Herzog: <https://psyche.co/ideas/what-might-mushroom-hunters-teach-the-doctors-of-tomorrow>

“interpreting the evidence in a way confirming the algorithm’s diagnosis” (Grote & Berens, 2020, p. 208; see also Henriksen & Bechmann, 2020). Also, this latter possibility poses the question of responsibility in its wider sense as distributed between algorithm designers, technical elements and users. Consequently, in summarizing the relevant, mainly ethical, literature, Grote and Berens (2020, p. 209) then conclude that we might need to shift our understanding of responsibility to a “less individualistic notions of responsibility, such as distributed or collective responsibility, to close potential ‘responsibility gaps’.” The growing body of literature illustrates a valuable pre-occupation with ethical reflections, but very little is known about how practices in healthcare relate to AIDSS and to the ethical issues posed by them. Therefore, ICU4Covid will have to address these questions in detail during the implementation process.

4.4 Bringing robotics to the ICU

The implementation of robotics in the ICU does not only introduce a new technology, but it also brings a new actor into the existing structures and processes. Cresswell and co-author’s (2018, p. 2) even describe it as a potentially ‘highly disruptive innovation’ due to its impact on everyday work practices. Based on the SSH framework that we have laid out in the **chapter 2**, the introduction of a new technology triggers the re-assembling of the ICU as a whole (see **chapter 2.2.2** for more). This is the case because the established links between the elements of the ICU – medical professionals, technologies, practices, regulations, etc. – are challenged and hence have to *come together in a new stable form*. Thereby, the question is not if robotics is ‘a solution or a problem?’ for healthcare in general, as the Think-Tank of the European Parliament asked in 2019, rather it is about the specific local contexts into which robotics are introduced. Taking into account the distinct user and knowledge ecologies (see **chapter 2.2.3** for more), that can be different from country to country but also from ICU to ICU, is, thus, a prerequisite in the process of implementing robotics of any kind into the ICU.

In general, it is important to consider the legacy of robotics as its specific historic development impacts today’s role in and for healthcare. The origins of commercial robotics can mainly be located in industrial contexts, where the optimization of production lines via automation and routinization was the main objective²⁶. The tasks that were delegated to such industrial robots were highly standardized in the sense that each robot on the assembly line does only conduct one specific task that never changes. According to Vallès-Peris and Domènech (2020) this notion of standardization is now transferred to the area of healthcare by the implementation of robotics. By introducing them into healthcare, care work is split up into two opposing categories of care activities: Those that are ‘tedious’ and those that are ‘heavy’; or those that are ‘emotional’ and those that are ‘real’ (Vallès-Peris & Domènech, 2020, p. 165). In everyday practice, healthcare workers are always confronted with the challenge of keeping the balance between these two categories: the individual needs of patients and the standardized procedures that are ever more prescribed by contemporary healthcare systems and institutions (Cresswell et al., 2018).

²⁶ Robot History, International Federation of Robotics: <https://ifr.org/robot-history>

There are various topics of research within SSH concerning robotics. In the following we will engage shortly with those topics that are relevant in specific for the application of a bedside robotic arm in ICUs. Generally speaking, introducing robotic arms to the ICU means a delegation of tasks that is in most cases coupled with a promise towards the healthcare workers that they will have more time for 'quality care'. This assumption is challenged from SSH perspectives. While a central aspect for the successful implementation of technological innovations is a pull from the stakeholders that it is supposed to benefit, SSH research shows an ambivalent position in this regard. Furthermore, it can demonstrate, that the level of automation and autonomy that a robot has and executes, impacts the attitude of healthcare workers towards this new technology. Finally, a strand of literature within SSH research engages with the relation of care, the body and technologies. In this context robotics might create a fundamental challenge to the way healthcare is practiced.

More innovation – more time?

The introduction of new technological innovations in general, but also specifically the introduction of robotics to the healthcare sector is often coupled with the promise that the delegation of tasks to the respective technologies will create 'free time' for the healthcare workers which they can then invest in what is referred to as 'quality care'. This assumption is challenged by different SSH perspectives. First, Vallès-Peris and Domènech (2020) have pointed to the historical legacy that led to the imagination that (health)care can be split into two opposing types of care. They make clear that this is not a distinction that has been made based on factual arguments, but rather on the transfer of the ways robotics are used from one field, that of industrial production, to another, that of healthcare. While there are certainly tasks that can be executed in a standardized manner, healthcare is a holistic practice. Struhkamp et al. (2009, p. 57) have pointed to the fact that everyday clinical work requires a specific "mode of knowing and acting". This 'doctoring', as they call it, is a form of situational and patient-oriented way of acting and addressing the individual needs of patients. According to them, doctoring is not a linear process but instead fuzzy and often uncertain. That is why the depiction of healthcare as a linear process, where single tasks can be dissolved out of the general process of caring, does not capture the situational clinical reality as, among others, described by Cresswell et al. (2018). This is especially true for the ICU in times of COVID-19. Medical professionals and nursing staff are confronted with a situation of uncertainty that requires a case-by-case treatment of the patients.

The idea of delegation has been discussed by SSH for various technologies and artifacts in the past (i.e. Akrich, 1992; Latour, 1992; Johnson, 1988). Even though earlier work in this realm has shown that the delegation of tasks takes over responsibilities from the human stakeholders involved, Akrich (1992), for example, has highlighted that this is not a unilateral process but that ultimately the implemented technologies can and will be used in other ways than intended.

Pull or push? Implementation challenges

There are certain factors that SSH research has identified to influence the process of implementing new technological innovations. One central aspect here is the existence of a 'pull' from the involved stakeholders. As Cresswell et al. (2018) show, if there is no active pull from stakeholders the chances for a successful implementation into their everyday work practices

decreases. In consequence, this means that a successful implementation of bedside robotic arms into the ICU requires a pro-active pull from those people working and hospitalized there. Such a pull cannot be created by just giving more (technical) information but can only be fostered by including these stakeholders in the process of creation and implementation. As proposed in the SSH framework (**chapter 2**), the idea of co-creation is thus not peripheral, but a central aspect to consider in the development and implementation of robotics to the ICU. Only by taking into account the actual needs of healthcare workers a pull for such a technology can be leveraged that ultimately creates acceptance for it. In this context, SSH research highlights that the developers of technologies base their design on implicit imagination(s) and experiences of users, that do not (necessarily) coincide with the actual users (Fischer, Östlund, & Peine, 2020). This is what Akrich calls 'I-Methodology' (1995, see also Akrich, 1992). To prevent this from happening, direct engagement with the stakeholders that will work with robotics in the ICU to incorporate their needs and desires is necessary.

Even though the simple provision of more information about a new technology to medical professionals, nursing staff and patients is not effective, the exposure to robotic technologies can be (Cresswell et al., 2018). Just as in other social contexts the missing experience and exposure (not the missing technical knowledge) creates more prejudices. It is thus central for the successful implementation of robotics to the ICU that the stakeholders can experience these robotic technologies themselves while being aware that they are and remain in charge of what these technologies are doing.

Degrees of automation and perceptive shifts

Building on the previous debate, the level of automation of robotics and its impact on the perception of the technology by users has been discussed broadly by SSH. Cresswell et al. (2018), for example, argue based on their research that a higher 'sociotechnical complexity' is attributed with lower trust in robotics' ability to provide sufficient support in healthcare. Semi-autonomous robotics are thereby viewed as causing less frictions for the medical professionals and the patients, while fully autonomous robotics are perceived to cause more. In the context of our SSH framework this means that the medical professionals are actually aware that technologies with a high level of autonomy will change their everyday work practices significantly. Put in our words: They are aware that the re-assembling that takes place affects more of the existing relations. Another point that SSH research has highlighted for the implementation of robotics in the area of healthcare is that people are in favour of the use of such technologies if they are used to *complement* the human medical professionals and not to *replace* them (Turkle, 2017). While there is a broad body of literature that engages with the public perception of robotics in healthcare (i.e. Boys et al., 2016; Broadbent et al., 2009), it remains important to consider those people that work with these technologies. Even though, in theory, every member of the public that participated in these studies could one day enter the healthcare system and thus get in touch with robotics, there is a difference between an abstract imagination of engaging with such technologies from a citizen-perspective and a concrete imagination that is based on actual everyday engagement.

Distancing – between physical and social

The appeal for 'social distancing' is central in most national and local strategies to prevent COVID-19 from spreading. Even though the wording creates some confusions, as it is ultimately about '*physical* distancing' not *social* distancing, it also affects the way healthcare can be practiced. While those working in the ICU have been aware of the potential risk of transmitting bacteria or viruses from one patient to another or from patient to staff, current regulations and guidelines still have a broader effect on safety measures. Durkin and colleagues (2020) problematize the current difficult situation as professional touching is an integral part of healthcare and for patients' recovery while at the same time it can be a threat in times of COVID-19. Nevertheless, professional touching is viewed as an important part of healthcare that cannot easily be dismissed (Wearn et al., 2019). From this we can take away that even though robotics can be used for supportive tasks in healthcare, that either take away heavy physical exertions from the nursing staff or help to stay safe during the current situation, they should not be seen as replacement for human care. In the case of ICU4Covid, this means that the bedside robotic arms should only be viewed as *temporary supportive* technologies that can be used when the specific situation makes it necessary (see the aspect of doctoring under the first point).

5 CONCLUSIONS

This report provides the social sciences and humanities (SSH) framework for putting in place a co-creation process for the implementation of a Cyber-Physical System for Telemedicine and Intensive Care (CPS4TIC) at the ICU Hubs participating in the ICU4Covid project. To achieve this, **chapter 2** outlined the values and practices that should guide the mission-oriented innovation process that the ICU4Covid project will engage in. To this end, we introduced and outlined the concept of Responsible Innovation (RI) and its implications for the project. We have then outlined the basic understanding of the concept of “co-creation” as practiced in the ICU4Covid project. There we have argued that co-creation is essential for the success of the project as it allows an implementation of CPS4TIC in a way that is caring, adaptable, sustainable and empowering (CASE) across different sites and healthcare environments. Next, **chapter 3** pointed to the discussions and policy frames on the European level related to the three technologies that are brought together in the ICU4Covid project, namely telemedicine, robotics and Artificial Intelligence (AI). Finally, **chapter 4** elaborated on the key observations from empirical work in the social sciences concerning these three technological realms covered in the ICU4Covid project. These insights into previous experiences and challenges can serve to guide our attention in the process of implementation and scaling when it comes to its social and societal dimensions.

Figure 5 - Tasks crucial for ICU4Covid from an SSH perspective

Informed by insights from SSH we have identified the following seven tasks (see also Figure 5) as crucial for realising a context-sensitive atmosphere of co-creation in the different ICU Hubs of the ICU4Covid project. Each of these tasks is a reference point for our potential contribution to a user-sensitive implementation of CPS4TIC in the ICU Hubs. Even though they have been separated for a better overview, they depend on and influence each other. Every task is complemented with three central questions that will be addressed in the following deliverables.

Establishing context-sensitive co-creation environments: a matter of “How”

A co-creation approach is essential for the successful and sustainable implementation of the different technologies. In the ICU4Covid the questions not so much a matter of “If” (if these technologies should be implemented), but much more “How.” As a non-straightforward, not generalizable process, it requires the careful formation of environments that remain sensitive to the different stakeholders’ local contexts as well as the different kinds of expertise, expectations and needs they bring to the table. These environments provide a space and is planning to create an atmosphere to facilitate the expression of these concerns and their translation into a common implementation framework. This framework enables collaboration and can serve as a possible blueprint for the rollout of CPS4TIC beyond ICU4Covid. The framework we have developed here supports these context-sensitive processes by asking:

- What are the specific local contexts in each country and ICU and what challenges do they pose?
- How can the different stakeholder positions be voiced and brought together in carefully crafted environments of co-creation?
- How can multilingualism and context-sensitivity of the co-creation environments be conceptualized for the rollout of CPS4TIC to other hospitals?

Co-creating implementation processes: a special challenge

The envisioned processes of co-creation in the ICU4Covid project poses the specific challenge of implementing already existing technologies into contexts that, likewise, have existed prior. The attention, then, needs to focus on processes of mutual adaptation that are still possible and on the ability to re-assemble the ICU without disturbing existing workflows. These considerations inform the following questions:

- What are different stakeholders’ expectations of and needs for the implementation process?
- How can mutual adaptability be ensured in the implementation process and beyond?
- How can we capture, document and transport the experiences from previous CPS4TIC implementations to upcoming ones?

Being attentive to diverse user ecologies

Technologies are implemented into and re-shape, what we call, user ecologies. These user ecologies cannot easily be anticipated or generalized for every country and ICU. Hence, our research needs to carefully map their emergence, the multiple stakeholders they consist of and the relations between them, during the implementation of CPS4TIC. The following questions can guide these efforts:

- How do the stakeholders relate to each other in the emergent user ecologies?

- What relations of power and what tensions between stakeholders come to light in the process?
- How can the multiple perspectives voiced within and across the different user ecologies be brought into conversation?

Assessing the impacts of the change process together

As new technologies are introduced into the ICU, the pre-existing components and relations between them need to be re-assembled in order to integrate these innovations. A key task within the co-creation environments to be established will be to assess these changes and to unpack their differential impacts. We thus need to ask:

- Who is affected by what processes of change?
- How do stakeholders experience these changes, how do they feel supported in their work and where are potential resistances?
- How can we establish feedback loops to reflect on these differential changes and align them in ways that create a stable work and care environment?

Reflecting the individual technologies and their combination

Each of the technologies to be implemented into the ICU comes with its own challenges that require consideration. At the same time, they need to be viewed together in their interaction, their overall integration into the socio-technical assemblage of the ICU and the coordination this requires. That is why we need to ask throughout the process:

- How do each of the new technologies challenge existing routines and relations in the ICU?
- How do these technologies 'overlap' in the everyday work and care environment and potentially create new and unexpected challenges?
- How do the actors in the ICU orchestrate the relations between the individual technologies, each with its own challenges?

Ensuring technical and socio-cultural interoperability

By introducing CPS4TIC into different hospital environments with differing routines, organizational and administrative arrangements and potentially slightly diverging understandings of healthcare practices, it is essential to not only be attentive to the technical interoperability of the systems, but also to the socio-cultural interoperability. The latter points to the fact that a successful collaboration across different sites and contexts needs to be attentive to the local specificities to be taken into account and coordinated. A technological solution, that only needs to be copied from one site to the next, therefore can only be considered as part of the solution. Also, the multiple social dimensions of this innovation need attention in order to assure successful implementation. With our framework we want to inquire:

- What are the specificities of the local contexts?
- What new skills/literacies become necessary for working in the re-assembled ICU and how do stakeholders at different sites develop them?
- How can we facilitate interoperability and the dissemination of skills/literacies for the broader rollout of CPS4TIC?

Considering the re-distribution of care and responsibility within change processes

ICU4Covid and the intensive use of patient bodily data re-distributes tasks, occupational roles and responsibilities, transforms understandings of what it means to provide care and calls for the development of new skills and sensibilities – all of this “on the go”, while everyday business of the hospital must continue. To better understand and support this process we ask the following questions:

- How does the implementation of CPS4TIC, particularly the transition phases, relate to the ongoing operations in the ICU and how can we ensure these are not disrupted?
- How do healthcare workers negotiate CPS4TIC in their understandings and practices of providing care?
- How are responsibilities attributed to the human and non-human actors in the socio-technical assemblages and how are they coordinated with existing regulatory frameworks?

This report has highlighted the importance to be attentive to the close relationships between the social and the technical and in consequence the need to understand the introduction of technological innovations into pre-existing ICU environments as a process *re-assembling*. Drawing on concepts from SSH research, we have established a solid conceptual framework that ensures the development of a fruitful environment for processes of co-creation and that is attuned to the complex challenges posed by the necessarily rapid implementation of a new socio-technical system as a response to an evolving crisis at different healthcare sites. To do this successfully, a close transdisciplinary collaboration all along the process of implementing CPS4TIC is necessary.

6 REFERENCES

- Akrich, M. (1992). The De-Description of Technical Objects. In W.E. Bijker & J. Law (Eds.), *Shaping Technology/Building Society: Studies in Sociotechnical Change* (pp. 205-224). Cambridge, MA and London: MIT Press.
- Akrich, M. (1995). User Representations: Practices, Methods and Sociology. In A. Rip, T.J. Misa & Schot, J. (Eds.), *Managing Technology in Society. The Approach of Constructive Technology Assessment* (pp. 167-184). London/New York: Pinter Publisher.
- Andersen, T. O. (2019). Large-scale and long-term co-design of digital health. *Interactions*, 5, 74-77. doi: 10.1145/3356252
- Armstrong, D. (1995). The rise of surveillance medicine. *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 17(3), 393–404. doi: 1467-9566.ep10933329
- Aula, V. (2019). Institutions, infrastructures, and data friction – Reforming secondary use of health data in Finland. *Big Data & Society*, 6(2), 1-13. doi: 10.1177/2053951719875980
- Bailey, S., Pierides, D., Brisley, A., Weisshaar, C., & Blakeman, T. (2020). Dismembering organisation: The coordination of algorithmic work in healthcare. *Current Sociology*, 68(4), 546–571. doi: 10.1177/0011392120907638
- Bammer, G. (2019). Key issues in co-creation with stakeholders when research problems are complex. *Evidence & Policy: A Journal of Research, Debate and Practice*, 15(3), 423-435. doi: 10.1332/174426419x15532579188099
- Bareiss, W. (2001). Telemedicine in South Dakota: A Cultural Studies Approach. *New Media & Society*, 3(3), 327–355. doi: 10.1177/14614440122226128
- Bastard, I., Gardon, D., Fouetillou, G., Prieur, C., & Raux, S. (2013). Travail et travailleurs de la donnée. Retrieved from <https://www.internetactu.net/2013/12/13/travail-et-travailleurs-de-la-donnee/>
- Bate, P., & Robert, G. (2006). Experience-based design: from redesigning the system around the patient to co-designing services with the patient. *Qual Saf Health Care*, 15(5), 307-310. doi:10.1136/qshc.2005.016527
- Bates, J. (2018). The politics of data friction. *Journal of Documentation*, 74(2), 412–429. doi: 10.1108/JD-05-2017-0080
- Bates, J., Lin, Y.-W., & Goodale, P. (2016). Data journeys: Capturing the socio-material constitution of data objects and flows. *Big Data & Society*, 3(2), 1-12. doi: 10.1177/2053951716654502
- Berg, M. (1997). *Rationalizing Medical Work. Decision-Support Techniques and Medical Practices*. Cambridge: MIT Press.

- Berg, M. (2001). Implementing information systems in health care organizations: Myths and challenges. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 64(2), 143–156. doi: 10.1016/S1386-5056(01)00200-3
- Bowker, G. C., Baker, K., Millerand, F., & Ribes, D. (2010). Toward Information Infrastructure Studies: Ways of Knowing in a Networked Environment. In J. Hunsinger, L. Klastrop, & M. Allen (Eds.), *International Handbook of Internet Research* (pp. 97–117). Springer Netherlands. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4020-9789-8_5
- Boys, J. A., Alicuben, E. T., DeMeester, M. J., Worrell, S. G., Oh, D. S., Hagen, J. A., & DeMeester, S. R. (2016). Public perceptions on robotic surgery, hospitals with robots, and surgeons that use them. *Surgical Endoscopy*, 30(4), 1310–1316. doi: 10.1007/s00464-015-4368-6
- Braun, M., Hummel, P., Beck, S., & Dabrock, P. (2020). Primer on an ethics of AI-based decision support systems in the clinic. *Journal of Medical Ethics*. doi: 10.1136/medethics-2019-105860
- Broadbent, E., Stafford, R., & MacDonald, B. (2009). Acceptance of healthcare robots for the older population: review and future directions. *International Journal of Social Robotics*, 1(4), 319–330. doi: 10.1007/s12369-009-0030-6
- Cartwright, L. (2001). Reach Out and Heal Someone. Rural Telemedicine and the Globalization of U.S. Health Care. In P. E. Brodwin (Ed.), *Biotechnology and Culture* (pp. 241–263). Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Castell, S., Cameron, D., Ginnis, S., Gottfried, G., & Maguire, K. (2017). *Public views of Machine Learning*. Retrieved from <https://royalsociety.org/~media/policy/projects/machine-learning/publications/public-views-of-machine-learning-ipsos-mori.pdf>
- Cresswell, K., Cunningham-Burley, S., & Sheikh, A. (2018). Health care robotics: qualitative exploration of key challenges and future directions. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 20(7), 1–11. doi: 10.2196/10410
- Collin-Jacques, C., & Smith, C. (2005). Nursing on the line: Experiences from England and Quebec (Canada). *Human Relations*, 58(1), 5–32. doi: 10.1177/0018726705050933
- Conde-Blanco, E., Centeno, M., Tio, E., Muriana, D., García-Peñas, J. J., Serrano, P., Nagel, A. G., Serratos, J., Jiménez, Á. P., Toledo, M., Donaire, A., Manzanares, I., Betrán, O., & Carreño, M. (2020). Emergency implementation of telemedicine for epilepsy in Spain: Results of a survey during SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. *Epilepsy & Behavior*, 111. doi: 10.1016/j.yebeh.2020.107211
- Coopmans, C. (2006). Making mammograms mobile: Suggestions for a sociology of data mobility. *Information, Communication & Society*, 9(1), 1–19. doi: 10.1080/13691180500519274
- Czarniawska, B. (2004). *Narratives in Social Science Research*. London: Sage Publications.
- Deleuze, G. (1992). Postscript on the Societies of Control. *October*, 59, 3–7.
- Demers-Payette, O., Lehoux, P., & Daudelin, G. (2016). Responsible research and innovation: A productive model for the future of medical innovation. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 3(3), 188–208. doi: 10.1080/23299460.2016.1256659

- DG Health and Food Safety. (2016). *Strategic Plan 2016-2020*. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/strategic-plan-2016-2020-dg-sante_en_0.pdf
- DG Health and Food Safety. (2021). *Assessment of the EU Member States' rules on health data in the light of GDPR*. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/health/files/ehealth/docs/ms_rules_health-data_en.pdf
- Dussauge, I., Helgesson, C.-F., & Lee, F. (Eds.). (2015). *Value Practices in the Life Sciences and Medicine*. Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Durkin, J., Jackson, D., & Usher, K. (2020). Touch in times of COVID-19: Touch hunger hurts. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 30(1-2), 4-5. doi: 10.1111/jocn.15488
- Dyb, K., & Halford, S. (2009). Placing Globalizing Technologies: Telemedicine and the Making of Difference. *Sociology*, 43(2), 232–249. doi: 10.1177/0038038508101163
- Eaves, E. R., Trotter, R. T., & Baldwin, J. A. (2020). Another Silver Lining? Anthropological Perspectives on the Promise and Practice of Relaxed Restrictions for Telemedicine and Medication-Assisted Treatment in the Context of COVID-19. *Human Organization*, 79(4), 292–303. doi: 10.17730/1938-3525-79.4.292
- EGE. (2018). *Artificial Intelligence, Robotics and 'Autonomous' Systems*. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/research/ege/pdf/ege_ai_statement_2018.pdf
- euRobotics. (2020). *Strategic Research, Innovation and Deployment Agenda. AI, Data and Robotics Partnership*. Retrieved from <https://www.eu-robotics.net/cms/upload/downloads/ppp-documents/AI-Data-Robotics-Partnership-SRIDA-V3.0.pdf>
- European Commission. (2010). *A Digital Agenda for Europe*. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52010DC0245&from=en>
- European Commission. (2018a). Communication on enabling the digital transformation of health and care in the Digital Single Market. Empowering citizens and building a healthier society. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/communication-enabling-digital-transformation-health-and-care-digital-single-market-empowering>
- European Commission. (2018b). *Market study on telemedicine*. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/health/files/ehealth/docs/2018_provision_marketstudy_telemedicine_en.pdf
- European Commission. (2018c). Artificial Intelligence for Europe. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/communication-artificial-intelligence-europe>
- European Commission. (2020). *White Paper on Artificial Intelligence - A European approach to excellence and trust*. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/commission-white-paper-artificial-intelligence-feb2020_en.pdf

- European Parliament. (2016). *European Civil Law Rules in Robotics*. Retrieved from [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2016/571379/IPOL_STU\(2016\)571379_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2016/571379/IPOL_STU(2016)571379_EN.pdf)
- European Parliament. (2019). *Robots in healthcare: a solution or a problem?* Retrieved from [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document.html?reference=IPOL_IDA\(2019\)638391](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document.html?reference=IPOL_IDA(2019)638391)
- Even Chorev, N. (2019). Data ambiguity and clinical decision making: A qualitative case study of the use of predictive information technologies in a personalized cancer clinical trial. *Health Informatics Journal*, 25(3), 500–510. doi: 10.1177/1460458219827355
- Felt, U. (2017). “Response-able Practices” or “New Bureaucracies of Virtue”: The Challenges of Making RRI Work in Academic Environments. In L. Asveld, R. van Dam-Mieras, T. Swierstra, S. Lavrijssen, K. Linse, & J. van den Hoven (Eds.), *Responsible Innovation 3: A European Agenda?* (pp. 49-68). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Felt, U. (2018). Responsible Research and Innovation. In S. Gibbon, B. Prainsack, S. Hilgartner, & J. Lamoreaux (Eds.), *Handbook of Genomics, Health and Society* (pp. 108-116). London/New York: Routledge.
- Felt, U., Wynne, B., Callon, M., Gonçalves, M. E., Jasanoff, S., Jepsen, M., Joly, P. B., Konopasek, Z., May, S., Neubauer, C., Rip, A., Siune, K. Stirling, A., & Tallacchini, M. (2007). *Taking European Knowledge Society Seriously*. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities.
- Felt, U., Öchsner, S., & Rae, R. (2019a). *Social Sciences and Humanities Framework Report. Framing the research, development and design processes when building a prototype of a citizen-centred interoperable health-data exchange platform*. Deliverable 1.1 of the Horizon2020 Project Smart4Health, Grant Agreement 826117. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3334262
- Felt, U., Öchsner, S., & Rae, R. (2019b). *Report on the methodological design of the co-creation environment*. Deliverable 1.2 of the Horizon2020 Project Smart4Health, Grant Agreement 826117. https://sts.univie.ac.at/fileadmin/user_upload/i_sts/Forschung/New_STS_Website/Smart4Health_D1.2_F1.0.pdf
- Felt, U., Öchsner, S., & Rae, R. (2020). The Making of Digital Health: Between Visions and Realizations. In J. Fritz & N. Tomaschek (Eds.), *Digitaler Humanismus* (pp. 89-101). Münster/New York: Waxmann Verlag.
- Fiore-Gartland, B., & Neff, G. (2015). Communication, Mediation, and the Expectations of Data: Data Valences Across Health and Wellness Communities. *International Journal of Communication*, 9, 1466-1484. doi: 1932–8036/20150005
- Fischer, B., Östlund, B., & Peine, A. (2020). Of robots and humans: Creating user representations in practice. *Social Studies of Science*, 50(2), 221-244. doi: 10.1177/0306312720905116

- Floridi, L., Cows, J., Beltrametti, M., Chatila, R., Chazerand, P., Dignum, V., Luetge, C., Madelin, R., Pagallo, U., Rossi, F., Schafer, B., Valcke, P., & Vayena, E. (2018). AI4People-An Ethical Framework for a Good AI Society: Opportunities, Risks, Principles, and Recommendations. *Minds Mach (Dordr)*, 28(4), 689–707. doi: 10.1007/s11023-018-9482-5
- Garnett, E. (2016). Developing a feeling for error: Practices of monitoring and modelling air pollution data. *Big Data & Society*, 3(2), 1-12. doi: 10.1177/2053951716658061
- Giddens, A. (1991). *Modernity and Self-Identity. Self and Society in the Late Modern Age*. Polity Press.
- Gille, F., Jobin, A., & Ienca, M. (2020). What we talk about when we talk about trust: Theory of trust for AI in healthcare. *Intelligence-Based Medicine*, 1-2. doi: 10.1016/j.ibmed.2020.100001
- Grönroos, C., Heinonen, K., & Strandvik, T. (2015). Value Co-creation: Critical Reflections. In J. Gummerus & C. von Koskull (Eds.), *The Nordic School - Service Marketing and Management for the Future* (pp. 69-80). Helsinki: Hanken School of Economics.
- Gray, J., Gerlitz, C., & Bounegru, L. (2018). Data infrastructure literacy. *Big Data & Society*, 5(2), 1-13. doi: 10.1177/2053951718786316
- Greenhalgh, T., Jackson, C., Shaw, S., & Janamian, T. (2016). Achieving Research Impact Through Co-creation in Community-Based Health Services: Literature Review and Case Study. *The Milbank Quarterly*, 94(2), 392-429. doi: 10.1111/1468-0009.12197
- Grisot, M., Moltubakk Kempton, A., Hagen, L., & Aanestad, M. (2019). Data-work for personalized care: Examining nurses' practices in remote monitoring of chronic patients. *Health Informatics Journal*, 25(3), 608–616. doi: 10.1177/1460458219833110
- Grol, R., Wensing, M., Eccles, M., & Davis, D. (Eds.). (2013). *Improving Patient Care. The Implementation of Change in Health Care*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons.
- Grote, T., & Berens, P. (2020). On the ethics of algorithmic decision-making in healthcare. *Journal of Medical Ethics*, 46(3), 205-221. doi: 10.1136/medethics-2019-105586
- Hagendorff, T. (2020). The Ethics of AI Ethics: An Evaluation of Guidelines. *Minds and Machines*, 30(1), 99–120. doi: s11023-020-09517-8
- Haggerty, K. D., & Ericson, R. V. (2000). The surveillant assemblage. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 51(4), 605–622. doi: 10.1080/00071310020015280
- Halford, S., Lotherington, A. T., Obstfelder, A., & Dyb, K. (2010). Getting the Whole Picture? *Information, Communication & Society*, 13(3), 442–465. doi: 10.1080/13691180903095856
- Hanlon, G., Strangleman, T., Goode, J., Luff, D., O’Cathain, A., & Greatbatch, D. (2005). Knowledge, technology and nursing: The case of NHS Direct. *Human Relations*, 58(2), 147–171. doi: 10.1177/0018726705052179
- Harris, A. (2021). *A Sensory Education*. London: Routledge.

- Hendy, J., Chrysanthaki, T., & Barlow, J. (2014). Managers' Identification with and Adoption of Telehealthcare. *Societies*, 4(3), 428–445. doi: 10.3390/soc4030428
- Henriksen, A., & Bechmann, A. (2020). Building truths in AI: Making predictive algorithms doable in healthcare. *Information, Communication & Society*, 23(6), 802–816. doi: 10.1080/1369118X.2020.1751866
- Hull, L., Goulding, L., Khadjesari, Z., Davis, R., Healey, A., Bakolis, I., & Sevdalis, N. (2019). Designing high-quality implementation research: development, application, feasibility and preliminary evaluation of the implementation science research development (ImpRes) tool and guide. *Implementation Science*, 14(1), 1-20. doi:10.1186/s13012-019-0897-z
- Johnson, J. (1988). Mixing humans and nonhumans together: The sociology of a door-closer. *Social Problems*, 35(3), 298-310. doi: 10.2307/800624
- Kamp, A., & Hansen, A. M. (2019). Negotiating Professional Knowledge and Responsibility in Cross-sectoral Telemedicine. *Nordic Journal of Working Life Studies*, 9(S5). doi: 10.18291/njwls.v9iS5.112691
- Kitchin, R. (2014). *The Data Revolution. Big data, Open Data, Data Infrastructures & their Consequences*. SAGE.
- Koops, B.-J., Oosterlaken, I., Romijn, H., Swierstra, T., & van den Hoven, J. (Eds.). (2015). *Responsible Innovation 2. Concepts, Approaches, and Applications*. Springer.
- Kotliar, D. M. (2021). Who Gets to Choose? On the Socio-algorithmic Construction of Choice. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 46(2), 346–375. doi: 10.1177/0162243920925147
- Latour, B. (1992). "Where Are the Missing Masses? The Sociology of a Few Mundane Artifacts". In W.E. Bijker and J. Law (Eds.), *Shaping Technology/Building Society: Studies in Sociotechnical Change* (pp. 225-259). Cambridge, MA and London: MIT Press.
- Latour, B. (2003). *Science in Action. How to Follow Scientists and Engineers through Society* (11th ed.). Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Latour, B. (2005). *Reassembling the Social: An Introduction to Actor-Network-Theory*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Latour, B., & Woolgar, S. (1986). *Laboratory Life. The Construction of Scientific Facts*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Lehoux, P., Sicotte, C., Denis, J.-L., Berg, M., & Lacroix, A. (2002). The theory of use behind telemedicine: How compatible with physicians' clinical routines? *Social Science & Medicine*, 54(6), 889–904. doi: 10.1016/S0277-9536(01)00063-6
- Lomborg, S., Langstrup, H., & Andersen, T. O. (2020). Interpretation as luxury: Heart patients living with data doubt, hope, and anxiety. *Big Data & Society*, 7(1), 1-13. doi: 10.1177/2053951720924436
- Lupton, D. (2015). Fabricated data bodies: Reflections on 3D printed digital body objects in medical and health domains. *Social Theory & Health*, 13(2), 99–115. doi: 10.1057/sth.2015.3

- Lupton, D. (2016). Digital companion species and eating data: Implications for theorising digital data–human assemblages. *Big Data & Society*, 3(1), 1–5. doi: 10.1177/2053951715619947
- Lupton, D. (2018). How do data come to matter? Living and becoming with personal data. *Big Data & Society*, 5(2), 1–11. doi: 10.1177/2053951718786314
- Lupton, D., & Maslen, S. (2017). Telemedicine and the senses: A review. *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 39(8), 1557–1571. doi: 10.1111/1467-9566.12617
- Lyon, D. (Ed.). (2003). *Surveillance as Social Sorting: Privacy, Risk, and Digital Discrimination*. Routledge.
- Mäkinen, S., Hyysalo, S., & Johnson, M. (2018). Ecologies of user knowledge: linking user insight in organisations to specific projects. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 31(3), 340–355. doi:10.1080/09537325.2018.1502874
- Mager, A., & Mayer, K. (2019). Body data—Data body: Tracing ambiguous trajectories of data bodies between empowerment and social control in the context of health. *Momentum Quarterly - Zeitschrift für sozialen Fortschritt*, 8(2), 95–108. doi: 10.15203/momentumquarterly.vol8.no2.p95-108
- Maslen, S. (2016). Sensory Work of Diagnosis: A Crisis of Legitimacy. *The Senses and Society*, 11(2), 158–176. doi: 10.1080/17458927.2016.1190065
- Matzner, T. (2016). Beyond data as representation: The performativity of Big Data in surveillance. *Surveillance & Society*, 14(2), 197–210. doi: 10.24908/ss.v14i2.5831
- McCadden, M. D., Joshi, S., Mazwi, M., & Anderson, J. A. (2020). Ethical limitations of algorithmic fairness solutions in health care machine learning. *The Lancet Digital Health*, 2(5), e221–e223. doi:10.1016/s2589-7500(20)30065-0
- Milne R., & Costa, A. (2020). Disruption and dislocation in post-COVID futures for digital health. *Big Data & Society*, 7(2), 1–5. doi: 10.1177/2053951720949567
- Miscione, G. (2007). Telemedicine in the Upper Amazon: Interplay with Local Health Care Practices. *Management Information Systems Quarterly*, 31(2).
- Mittelstadt, B. (2019). Principles alone cannot guarantee ethical AI. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 1, 501–507. doi: 10.2139/ssrn.3391293
- Mittelstadt, B. D., Allo, P., Taddeo, M., Wachter, S., & Floridi, L. (2016). The ethics of algorithms: Mapping the debate. *Big Data & Society*, 3(2), 1–21. doi: 10.1177/2053951716679679
- Mol, A. (2002). *The Body Multiple. Ontology in Medical Practice*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- Mort, M., Finch, T., & May, C. (2009). Making and Unmaking Telepatients: Identity and Governance in New Health Technologies. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 34(1), 9–33. doi: 10.1177/0162243907311274

- Mort, M., May, C. R., & Williams, T. (2003). Remote Doctors and Absent Patients: Acting at a Distance in Telemedicine? *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 28(2), 274–295. doi: 10.1177/0162243902250907
- Nadim, T. (2016). Data Labours: How the Sequence Databases GenBank and EMBL-Bank Make Data. *Science as Culture*, 25(4), 496–519. doi: 10.1080/09505431.2016.1189894
- Neff, G. (2013). Why Big Data Won't Cure Us. *Big Data*, 1(3), 117–123. doi: 10.1089/big.2013.0029
- Neff, G., Tanweer, A., Fiore-Gartland, B., & Osburn, L. (2017). Critique and Contribute: A Practice-Based Framework for Improving Critical Data Studies and Data Science. *Big Data*, 5(2), 85–97. doi: 10.1089/big.2016.0050
- Nettleton, S. (2004). The Emergence of E-Scaped Medicine? *Sociology*, 38(4), 661–679. doi: 10.1177/0038038504045857
- Nicolini, D. (2006). The work to make telemedicine work: A social and articulative view. *Social Science & Medicine*, 62(11), 2754–2767. doi: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2005.11.001
- Nicolini, D. (2007). Stretching out and expanding work practices in time and space: The case of telemedicine. *Human Relations*, 60(6), 889–920. doi: 10.1177/0018726707080080
- Oudshoorn, N. (2008). Diagnosis at a distance: The invisible work of patients and healthcare professionals in cardiac telemonitoring technology. *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 30(2), 272–288. doi: 10.1111/j.1467-9566.2007.01032.x
- Oudshoorn, N. (2009). Physical and digital proximity: Emerging ways of health care in face-to-face and telemonitoring of heart-failure patients. *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 31(3), 390–405. doi: 10.1111/j.1467-9566.2008.01141.x
- Oudshoorn, N. (2012). How places matter: Telecare technologies and the changing spatial dimensions of healthcare. *Social Studies of Science*, 42(1), 121–142. doi: 10.1177/0306312711431817
- Oudshoorn, N., & Pinch, T. (2003). *How Users Matter; The Co-Construction of Users and Technology*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Ostherr, K., Borodina, S., Bracken, R. C., Lotterman, C., Storer, E., & Williams, B. (2017). Trust and privacy in the context of user-generated health data. *Big Data & Society*, 4(1). doi: 10.1177/2053951717704673
- Owen, R., & Pansera, M. (2019). *Responsible innovation and responsible research and innovation*. In *Handbook on science and public policy*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Pappas, Y., & Seale, C. (2009). The opening phase of telemedicine consultations: An analysis of interaction. *Social Science & Medicine*, 68(7), 1229–1237. doi: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2009.01.011
- Petersson, J. (2011). Medicine at a Distance in Sweden: Spatiotemporal Matters in Accomplishing Working Telemedicine. *Science & Technology Studies*, 24(2), 43–63. doi: 10.23987/sts.55263

- Petersson, J. (2016). Technospatialities and telehealthcare: Unfolding new spaces of visibility. *Information, Communication & Society*, 19(6), 824–842. doi: 10.1080/1369118X.2015.1061575
- Pink, S., Ruckenstein, M., Willim, R., & Duque, M. (2018). Broken data: Conceptualising data in an emerging world. *Big Data & Society*, 5(1). doi: 10.1177/2053951717753228
- Pinnock, H., Barwick, M., Carpenter, C. R., Eldridge, S., Grandes, G., Griffiths, C. J., Rycroft-Malone, J., Meissner, P., Murray, E., Patel, A., Sheikh, A., & Taylor, S. J. C.. (2017). Standards for Reporting Implementation Studies (StaRI) Statement. *BMJ*, 356, i6795. doi: 10.1136/bmj.i6795
- Pols, J. (2012). *Care at a distance on the closeness of technology*. Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press.
- Pollock, N., & Williams, R. (2010). e-Infrastructures: How Do We Know and Understand Them? Strategic Ethnography and the Biography of Artefacts. *Computer Supported Cooperative Work (CSCW)*, 19(6), 521-556. doi:10.1007/s10606-010-9129-4
- Pope, C., Halford, S., Turnbull, J., Prichard, J., Caletani, M., & May, C. (2013). Using computer decision support systems in NHS emergency and urgent care: Ethnographic study using normalisation process theory. *BMC Health Services Research*, 13(1), 111. doi: 10.1186/1472-6963-13-111
- Prahalad, C. K., & Venkat Ramaswamy. (2004). Co-creation experiences: The next practice in value creation. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 18(3), 5-14.
- Proctor, E. K., Powell, B. J., & McMillen, J. C. (2013). Implementation strategies: recommendations for specifying and reporting. *Implementation Science*, 8, 1-11. doi: 10.1186/1748-5908-8-139
- Raposo, V. L. (2016). Telemedicine: The legal framework (or the lack of it) in Europe. *GMS Health Technology Assessment*, 12, 1-12. doi: 10.3205/hta000126
- Rességuier, A., & Rodrigues, R. (2020). AI ethics should not remain toothless! A call to bring back the teeth of ethics. *Big Data & Society*, 7(2), 1-5. doi: 10.1177/2053951720942541
- Reubi, D. (2018). A genealogy of epidemiological reason: Saving lives, social surveys and global population. *BioSocieties*, 13(1), 81–102. doi: 10.1057/s41292-017-0055-2
- Ross, J., Stevenson, F., Dack, C., Pal, K., May, C., Michie, S., Barnard, M., & Murray, E. (2018). Developing an implementation strategy for a digital health intervention: an example in routine healthcare. *BMC Health Service Research*, 18(1), 1-13. doi: 10.1186/s12913-018-3615-7
- Ruckenstein, M., & Schüll, N. D. (2017). The Datafication of Health. *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 46(1), 261–278. doi: 10.1146/annurev-anthro-102116-041244
- Samuelsson, T., & Berner, B. (2013). Swift Transport versus Information Gathering: Telemedicine and New Tensions in the Ambulance Service. *Journal of Contemporary Ethnography*, 42(6), 722–744. doi: 10.1177/0891241613488941
- Schwennesen, N. (2019). Algorithmic assemblages of care: Imaginaries, epistemologies and repair work. *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 41(S1), 176–192. doi: 10.1111/1467-9566.12900

- SIENNA. (2020). D4.7: *An Ethical framework for the development and use of AI and robotics technologies*. Retrieved from https://sienna-project.eu/digitalAssets/801/c_801912-l_1-k_d4.7_ethical-framework-for-ai--robotics_v2.pdf
- Smith, A. J., Pfister, B. F., Woo, E. W. Y., Walters, B. J., Blacket, B., Page, N., & Drobetz, H. (2020). Safe and rapid implementation of telemedicine fracture clinics: The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. *ANZ Journal of Surgery*, *90*(11), 2237–2241. doi: 10.1111/ans.16339
- Star, S. L. (Ed.) (1995). *Ecologies of Knowledge. Work and Politics in Science and Technology*. Albany: State University of New York Press.
- Star, S. L., & Ruhleder, K. (1996). Steps Toward an Ecology of Infrastructure: Design and Access for Large Information Spaces. *Information Systems Research*, *7*(1), 111–134. doi: 10.1287/isre.7.1.111
- Stilgoe, J., Owen, R., & Macnaghten, P. (2013). Developing a framework for responsible innovation. *Research Policy*, *42*(9), 1568–1580. doi:10.1016/j.respol.2013.05.008
- Tanriverdi, H., & Iacono, C. S. (1999). Diffusion of Telemedicine: A Knowledge Barrier Perspective. *Telemedicine Journal*, *5*(3), 223–244. doi: 10.1089/107830299311989
- Struhkamp, R., Mol, A., & Swierstra, T. (2009). Dealing with in/dependence: doctoring in physical rehabilitation practice. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, *34*(1), 55–76. doi: 10.1177/0162243907312954
- Torenholt, R., & Langstrup, H. (2021). Between a logic of disruption and a logic of continuation: Negotiating the legitimacy of algorithms used in automated clinical decision-making. *Health*, 1–19. doi: 10.1177/1363459321996741
- Turkle, S. (2017). *Alone together: Why we expect more from technology and less from each other*. New York: Basic Books.
- Vallès-Peris, N., & Domènech, M. (2020). Roboticians' Imaginaries of Robots for Care: The Radical Imaginary as a Tool for an Ethical Discussion. *Engineering Studies*, *12*(3), 157–176. doi: 10.1080/19378629.2020.1821695
- van den Hoven, J., Jacob, K., Nielsen, L., Roure, F., Rudze, L., Stilgoe, J., Blind, K., Guske, A. L., & Martinez Riera, C. (2013). *Options for Strengthening Responsible Research and Innovation. Report of the Expert Group on the State of Art in Europe on Responsible Research and Innovation*. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/document_library/pdf_06/options-for-strengthening_en.pdf
- van Dijk-de Vries, A., Stevens, A., van der Weijden, T., & Beurskens, A. (2020). How to support a co-creative research approach in order to foster impact. The development of a Co-creation Impact Compass for healthcare researchers. *PLOS One*, *15*(10), 1–16. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0240543
- Venturini, T., Jacomy, M., Meunier, A., & Latour, B. (2017). An unexpected journey: A few lessons from sciences Po médialab's experience. *Big Data & Society*, *4*(2). doi: 10.1177/2053951717720949

von Schomberg, R. (Ed.) (2011). *Towards Responsible Research and Innovation in the Information and Communication Technologies and Security Technologies Fields*. Brussels: European Commission.

von Schomberg, R. (2013). A vision of responsible innovation. In R. Owen, M. Heintz, & J. Bessant (Eds.), *Responsible Innovation* (pp. 51-74). London: John Wiley.

Wearn, A., Clouder, L., Barradell, S., & Neve, H. (2019). A qualitative research synthesis exploring professional touch in healthcare practice using the threshold concept framework. *Advances in Health Sciences Education, 25*, 731–754. doi: 0.1007/s10459-019-09901-9

Webster, A. (2002). Innovative Health Technologies and the Social: Redefining Health, Medicine and the Body. *Current Sociology, 50*(3), 443–457. doi: 10.1177/0011392102050003009